

Bringing cities to life, bringing life into cities

Deliverable 11

Report on progress of nature-based solution implementation

DOCUMENT PROPERTIES

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1. Executive summary

Mainstreaming Actions

From its outset, the ambition of Connecting Nature (CN) was clear: to **support cities in delivering a scaled up nature-based solutions (NBS) project** and also, importantly, to **bring together global innovation and state-of-the art to support cities on a journey towards mainstreaming nature-based solutions in policy and practice**. Whilst barriers and drivers have evolved across the duration of the project, a summary of those identified by the cities at the start of their journeys was presented in Deliverable 8. These barriers represent a multifaceted challenge, with complex universal, and unique, barriers in every city. Within Connecting Nature, the mechanisms required for mainstreaming were embedded into the parameters of the Framework. Developed with the Front Runner Cities, these comprise: Technical Solutions; Governance; Financing and business models; Nature-based enterprises; Co-production, Impact Assessment, and Reflexive Monitoring. The aim of these Elements being to provide a holistic suite of tools and approaches to enable local authority teams to co-produce a transition towards mainstreaming.

As represented by the infinity loop of the Connecting Nature framework figure, there is no singular entry point for this mainstreaming process. This is reflected in the three Front Runner City approaches. Each adopted a very different process for embedding and implementing the Framework, each starting from different elements and working through different strategies, depending on the experience of the city, the governance structures at the start of the process, and the skills of the Connecting Nature team. Working in partnership with the Front Runner Cities through this process provided a unique insight into not only how each city approached it, but also how these approaches compared and contrasted. What was clear from this overview, was that no single approach to tackling this complex challenge could be evaluated as being optimal, and that **a key part of mainstreaming nature-based solutions in cities is an organic self-learning trial and error approach to the Framework elements**.

For **Glasgow, this involved a very top-down approach**. Due to the ability of the CN team to influence at a decision-maker level, and their strategic role within the local authority, the approach was to embed NBS into city-wide policy. Once embedded, the policy was used to raise awareness and to engage stakeholders and financiers across the city to co-create NBS into open spaces. A key component to this has been building a strong evidence-base through a comprehensive impact evaluation and data sharing approach to empower stakeholders with the knowledge necessary for key decision-making.

In contrast, **Genk adopted a much more bottom-up approach**. The focus was on establishing a clear governance process that engaged not just city colleagues, but local citizens in the potential for the nature-based solution exemplar. With a strong focus on communication and branding, the Stiemer Deals programme ensured that community ownership was central to the exemplar development, and subsequent stewardship. This empowerment was then used as a lever to unlock new funding streams at city and regional levels to transform practices, previously focused on grey infrastructure, to drive nature-based solution delivery. This success has unlocked awareness across the city council of how nature-based solutions approaches to urban planning can deliver across strategic policy in the city.

In **Poznań, exemplar development began at a foundational level**, using the city's past experiences and legacy of a 'green wedge' urban design to raise awareness of the potential of nature-based solutions to deliver benefits to its communities. The development of the exemplar built from this foundation through an evidence-based pilot out-scaling approach. Successful implementation of the first natural playgrounds was used to engage colleagues across the council, and new kindergartens, to buy into the vision for replication across the city. This momentum underpinned the unlocking of additional usually disparate budgets into a shared vision, and underpinned the development of a new nature-based industry for the design and delivery of the playgrounds. Once local authority budgets were at capacity, the successful demonstration of the out-scaling enabled engagement of the private sector to unlock additional financing.

Whilst all three Front Runner Cities achieved inspirational success in terms of realising their vision, and truly transformational progress in terms of the nature-based solution mainstreaming pathway, at the time of this Deliverable, all city teams reflected that there was still more development needed to reach a situation whereby nature-based solutions were truly embedded at a city-wide scale. Similarly to the Framework process, the gaps to achieving this ambition were a blend of universal and unique across the Front Runner Cities.

Mainstreaming Gaps

Those that were common to all cities included the fundamental concept of **lack of understanding of what comprises nature-based solutions amongst stakeholders**. The Narratives workshops, the results of which are included in this document, have aimed at empowering the cities to use storytelling as a communication mechanism, both for their particular exemplar but also, by extent, as a way of communicating complex concepts such as NBS to a variety of audiences. It is clear that, from the beginning of the project to now, the evolution of understanding of this concept has transformed substantially. Nevertheless, at a senior decision-maker level, and at a community level there remain pockets of skepticism in relation to investing in nature-based solutions over more traditional and familiar grey infrastructure solutions.

Central to this was a **lack of evidence of the benefits of such approaches**. All three Front Runner Cities varied in their level of experience of impact evaluation of nature-based solutions. What experience there was ranged from an informal 'we know what works' approach to more formal but still extremely limited approaches. All three cities have engaged and developed impact evaluation capacity through Connecting Nature to build an evidence-base on the biodiversity, environment, social, and economic benefits of their nature-based solution exemplars. However, gaps remain in relation to ensuring that such evaluation is mainstreamed beyond the Connecting Nature programme and also, as this is such a new process for the cities, the **evidence from this is used effectively to unlock further mainstreaming**, and to ensure effective stewardship of existing solutions.

Another significant gap relates to financing. In all three Front Runner Cities, financing for nature-based solutions has been significantly scaled, including bringing new and diverse funding streams online. However, in order to deliver their visions of nature-based solutions embedded across each city at a scale to benefit and adapt all communities to climate change, **there is a need to scale this financing further**. Critical to this is continued silo-busting across the council departments. All three Front Runner Cities made good progress in relation to the **governance of interdepartmental working**. However, in order to unlock all of the potential benefits of nature-based solutions, there is a need to continue and expand this progress across all departments, to ensure that a nature-positive approach is at the heart of all policy and budgetary decisions.

Capacity in relation to delivery represents another critical universal gap. In each Front Runner City, the Connecting Nature team has substantially upskilled in relation to NBS expertise over the duration of the project. However, to continue to expand nature-based solution delivery over greater scales, **there is a need to transition project leadership to a broader base of nature-based solution delivery agents**. In order to achieve this, there is a need to expand the vision and expertise developed through Connecting Nature to other stakeholders across the city.

Lastly, long-term stewardship represents another gap to mainstreaming. Whilst stewardship plans were developed as part of each City's approach to the Framework, due to the short duration of the Connecting Nature project, and the time it takes to develop and deliver an exemplar on the scale and ambition of these, there was insufficient time to implement long-term stewardship that takes an adaptive approach to changing context and needs. As nature-based solutions are scaled more widely, **stewardship approaches will also need to be scaled in tandem**. Whilst the front runner cities began this process through collaboration with communities and non-governmental organisations, and by incubating nature-based enterprises, this component of the Framework scaling remains in its infancy.

Policy recommendations

To support cities in addressing these gaps, and to ensure the legacy of the transformative approaches initiated in Connecting Nature, there are a number of strategic priorities that would be recommended that emerged from the Front Runner City (FRC) Reflexive Monitoring and Peer-to-Peer sessions:

Within Connecting Nature, the FRC Reflexive Monitoring was supported by the Connecting Nature Framework leads through a review panel-style process. This was integral to supporting the FRCs engagement with the Framework and development of their exemplars. During the latter half of the project this process was transitioned to one whereby the FRCs played a mentoring role to the Fast Follower Cities (FFCs). This, combined with other peer-to-peer processes established between cities in the project, proved invaluable in terms of knowledge sharing, awareness raising, and capacity building. In order to ensure continued development and expansion of engagement with the Framework, and NBS mainstreaming in general, to other cities and stakeholders, **it is vital that such peer-to-peer learning processes are embedded into policy and practice**.

To support engagement with the Framework, wider rollout, and more effective nature-based solution implementation, it was also apparent that **more clarity in terms of a definition of nature-based solutions is needed**. As the IUCN are attempting currently, defining standard criteria for the fundamental components of a nature-based solution approach would be of great value, particularly in relation to developing criteria specific for urban nature-based solutions. What is clear is that nature-based solutions has the potential to become a catch-all term for any greening process. In order to unlock the potential for delivering simultaneous environmental, social and economic benefits through locally-contextualised *nature positive* actions, cities need more defined criteria from which, like Poznań, they can develop resources to raise awareness of, and effective deployment of, nature-based solutions.

Central to a stronger definition and standard, **is building a more complete evidence-base of the impact of nature-based solutions**. Whilst the Connecting Nature Front Runner Cities are developing this evidence, it was clear that there is a universal need across cities for a greater depth of understanding of both the certainty and uncertainty of nature-based solution delivery. To achieve this, there is a need for standardised evaluation criteria across the range of scales and types of benefits. There is also a **need for policy & legislation-based enforcement of long-term evaluation of nature-based solutions**, particularly through investment and development implementation pathways. It is important to continue exploring new and innovative ways to resource long-term evaluation.

At the heart of this evaluation needs to be an **assessment of the value of biodiversity and the contribution that nature-based solutions can make to this**. To unlock mainstreaming of nature-based solutions in urban planning, biodiversity value needs to be at least as mainstreamed as carbon markets are currently. Only when the vital role that biodiversity plays in global health is appropriately recognised, will the level of funding needed to unlock nature-based solution mainstreaming be available. Similarly to the current embeddedness of carbon 'cost', building this evidence base for the contribution of biodiversity through nature-based solutions will unlock mainstreaming of biodiversity as a cornerstone of socio-economic policy.

Once such valuation is mainstreamed, it will be vital that internal processes are updated to reflect such change. Of direct relevance to this, from all Front Runner Cities, was the challenge created by procurement policies that tend to favour the most cost-effective grey solutions over nature-based solutions. There is a **fundamental need to develop procurement processes that could favour solutions with more diverse benefits and co-benefits**, some of which could not be quantified as direct monetary values, over single or narrow function grey infrastructure solutions with narrow but easily quantified benefits. Allowing for co-creation processes with (by definition) undefined outcomes within procurement contracts also represented a significant policy challenge across the Front Runner Cities.

Lastly, across the Front Runner Cities, it was apparent that there was a **need to drive innovation in nature-based enterprises to support the mainstreaming of nature-based solution products and services**. Policy mechanisms that support innovation and entrepreneurship in this sector, including social impact investment and business acceleration and incubation, could provide a vital tool for developing a nature-based economy that drives nature-based solutions planning, delivery, and stewardship.

Narratives and Framework Figures

As part of a collaborative effort between WPs 2,3 and 4, including partners BioAzul and Climate Alliance, the Front-Runner Cities and Fast-Follower Cities participated in a series of workshops on Narrative and Storytelling for the Connecting Nature Framework. The purpose of the workshops was for the cities to become familiar with narrative

techniques and theory, to be able to tell the story of their exemplar in their own way and be able to adjust it for each use. For this purpose, we developed a number of innovative story-telling techniques that work in both text and image form; the identification of transformation points and trademarks. The framework figure was then developed to illustrate each city's individual narrative in a single image, a communication tool that they can use for multiple purposes. The following report uses the Front-Runner Cities's own language and figures, to tell the story of their transformation through Connecting Nature.

Transformation points

To begin thinking about the process of storytelling, the cities were encouraged to identify their points of Transformation. These could include any point within the duration of the project that (at the time or retrospectively) could be identified as a point of change or learning in their exemplar's journey. The points of Transformation could be identified by reflecting on the city's learning throughout the project. For example through processes such as the Reflexive Monitoring Critical Turning Points. By starting from these, a timeline could be created that illustrates Connecting Nature's impact on each exemplar. These moments can be graphically inserted onto the loop of the figure, indicating a point in time that reflects the stage at which it took place. For the cities, the team effort of identifying these points was a moment of reflection on the past few years and an opportunity to consider their learning and development through their involvement in Connecting Nature.

City Strengths

The cities could also use the CN Framework and figure to talk about their "trademarks"; elements of the CN Framework that they had learned the most through and they felt they had gained some expertise in. By identifying these, the cities could elaborate on their learning and become empowered through their narratives while claiming ownership of their story.

Once the cities submitted their forms, this data was compiled into each city's individual Framework Figure by BioAzul, illustrating their journey in Connecting Nature.

Process

To be able to create their individual figures, the cities were given a set of tables that they could use as teams to reflect on their Connecting Nature journey (Appendix)

Step 1: Cities were encouraged to reflectively identify their Points of Transformation up to this point

Step 2: In a similar way, City teams could then identify their City Strengths or 'Trademarks'.

Step 3: The Cities could allocate a degree of importance to each framework element for the Planning, Delivery and Stewardship phase. This is reflected in the figure as different sized bubbles.

Step 4: The Cities could add any images they would like to see presented in their figure, or propose illustrations that reflect their experiences.

The Narrative-making process is being developed into a guidebook to be published next year.

3.Genk

Nature-based solutions mainstreaming process

Genk's narrative

Genk exemplar: the Stiemer Valley

Description: The Stiemer is a forgotten stream that flows through Genk for about 8 km and is under severe pressure. Connecting to a unique wetland area the stream plays a critical role in local ecological integrity. The exemplar will re-imagine the natural quality of a stream valley in an urban context, delivering ecological, environmental, social, and economic benefits through a co-creation approach with local residents and businesses.

Societal challenges addressed:

- Regeneration of an underused and neglected natural capital asset.
- Stormwater management and green space management (including enhancing/ conserving urban biodiversity) to create an attractive and functional blue-green zone turning a neglected area into the jewel in the crown of Genk.
- Urban regeneration of an active travel route with links to enterprise zones.
- Participatory planning and governance through active participation from the local population feeding into the new landscape.
- Social justice and social cohesion through locals and tourists alike (re)discovering a previous neglected area through active travel, nature, and amenity.

Figure 1. Genk's framework figure

Genk have chosen to use the figure template to tell the story in a unique way. Through identifying their points of transformation and trademarks, they have created their narrative based on the Connecting Nature framework.

1. From project to program- planning phase

By not considering the Stiemer exemplar as a project anymore, but rather as a process/program has led to an entire new governance model. This transformed the entire approach in a fundamental way.

2. Investing in social innovation – Planning and Delivery phases

Deliberately choosing to allocate dedicated capacity to social innovation has boosted our co-production & participatory approach. We evolved in collaboration to real co-production based solutions such as the Stiemerdeals concept.

3. Awarded the city innovation fund – Delivery phase

Stiemer being selected as one of laureates of the Flemish City Innovation Fund is not only a financial lever, but also gives the programme and NBS as solution concept a lot of recognition and credibility.

4. Governance – Planning and Delivery phases

The governance model that we developed over the years in the planning phase is a core fundament of our programme, and gives ourselves and our partners guidance and clarity in the complexity of the project, also in the delivery phase.

5. Reflexive Monitoring

Together with DRIFT, we pioneered an advanced process monitoring approach (Reflexive monitoring) that for us feels as the main driving force behind the success of the Stiemer exemplar. A (well thought) learning process is often forgotten in urban planning, and we are happy that we managed to develop an approach that truly has built up our urban transformation capacity and is constantly improving our process/programme

Mainstreaming figure

Figure 2. Genk's transformation pathway for mainstreaming nature-based solutions. A self-reflection by the city CN team in relation to their transformation during the Connecting Nature project.

Technical Solutions

Technical Solutions has focused on four transformation projects designed to incrementally deliver the Stiemervallei vision and to engage stakeholders in the broader NBS project ambitions:

Current status of spatial transformation projects:

SuDS & Soda – implementation of this innovative Sustainable Drainage Systems (SuDS) project is underway. New to the Flemish region, this project is **delivering a new water cycle SuDS experimental approach that includes a focus on entrepreneurship**. Implementation of a SuDS Living Lab is beginning Autumn 2021 and will be completed in early 2022. The Living Lab is the first phase of broader SuDS rollout on public and private land, managing stormwater, improving the water quality, and enhancing biodiversity throughout the Stiemer Valley. The Living Lab will be used to increase the visibility of SuDS approaches and will lay a foundation for broader rollout in 2023 by introducing the community to the water cycle and the value of SuDS. An external consortium is building this demonstration site which will act as a catalyst for the Water Strategy Masterplan, scaling SuDS approaches in all neighbourhoods around the Stiemervallei. Everything is in place for implementation: the public domain component design is almost ready; the private domain and Living Lab (with new external consortium playing a key role) is ready for delivery. All of these delivery tracks will be up and running in the coming month. The overall outcome being using SuDS to prevent stormwater overflow in the catchment of the Stiemervallei. The water company – Aquafin - are financing the installation of the SuDS. As this is a significant shift for them from funding grey to green infrastructure, it is also a key learning/pilot experiment for them at a Flemish regional level.

Slagmolen – this project comprises the **redesign of green/blue infrastructure areas of the Slagmolen as part of a flood mitigation and renaturalisation programme**. The project area forms the gateway from the City of Genk to the Natura2000 area ‘De Maten’ - a wetland system highly dependent on sufficient and high quality water to support its water-dependent ecosystems rich in biodiversity. Regular combined sewer overflows from the Stiemerbeek bring poor quality water to this pond system, threatening its ecological integrity. As part of the Stiemervallei exemplar, design plans have started for Phase 2 of this nature-based solution approach. Co-creation design and planning activities have been undertaken. A delay of 6 months has arisen due to complex hydrology in the project area, revealed by monitoring and recent flooding following implementation of the Phase 1 project. In 2022, preparation for implementation will be carried out with implementation of the nature-based solution approach due to start in Spring 2023.

Gardens of Waterschei – this Stiemervallei **transformation project is focused on the use of biodiversity enhancement to create a green lung connecting the key city assets of Thor Park (renewable energy campus) Stalenstraat (key retail street)**, the ambition being to stimulate environmental, social and economic benefits for the entrepreneurs of Stalenstraat by restoring a more natural water system, increasing the connection with nature, and with other districts surrounding the Stiemerbeek. The first phase of this project has been constructed with a new blue/green terrace pilot intervention now opened. The second phase, the creation of a physical Stiemer Hub is also underway with a 6-month co-design and development programme managed by an external process/co-creation expert. On completion, the Stiemer Hub will provide an experimental environment to catalyse the Stiemervallei’s Stiemer Deals programme, providing a physical space to enhance the quintuple helix stakeholder interaction. The deadline for the first phase of completion is the end April 2022 with launch of the building overlooking the Stiemer Valley, including surrounding green/blue infrastructure, scheduled for the Genk Innovation Summit.

Vallei Route – using nature-based solutions to deliver an active travel route through the Stiemervallei. This spatial transformation project has a similar timeline to the other projects. Contracted partner Tractebel will develop the technical design, following this, there will be a need to manage the planning and procurement processes, with implementation beginning in spring 2022.

Governance

The Stiemervallei project organic top-down opportunity-driven approach and bottom-up convergence of small and large projects and visions represented an organizational challenge for the small Environment & Sustainable Development Department within the City of Genk. Initiated as horizontal working process bridging multidisciplinary consultative bodies in sub-projects, **it was necessary to shift to program-based governance approach**, with a clear implementation strategy for integrating the various sub-projects. Instead of the sum of project structures, this required a clear and integrated governance model characterized by a horizontal, co-creative approach in which involvement of stakeholders, both internal (other departments) and external (other agencies, NGOs, businesses and citizens), and ownership are central principles.

The innovative collaborative governance model developed for the Stiemervallei NBS programme, is now being mainstreamed across other major city programmes (e.g. Energy Sector).

Scaled-up greening across the city is now being mainstreamed in the next policy round. **Social and ecological benefits of nature-based solutions are being increasingly recognised and adopted across the city departments.** The exception, perhaps, being economic mainstreaming of nature-based solutions as drivers for a nature-based economy across the city, which is still less well embedded in city policy and strategy.

The grant received for SUDs & SODA can indeed be considered as an innovation and breakthrough, because **a traditional funding mechanism for sewage infrastructure has been opened up**; a new category for experimenting with NBS was added under pressure of 2 Flemish cities (one of them being Genk).

Through Stiemerdeals – public-private cooperations on human scale, Genk managed to increase the resources (personnel, financial) being invested in the programme.

A shift in the structure of Working Groups within the City from project-based to thematic-based (e.g. Water Management) has enabled a **more strategic and integrated approach to project delivery**, that also has more influence due to Working Group members typically being more senior within organisation and strategic levels.

In addition, through the 2020 Policy Cycle, sustainability is now embedded as one of three horizontal topics with **Climate Action Planning and Nature-based Solutions now mainstreamed on delivery agendas of colleagues across the city authority.** This includes transfer of the nature-based solution concept to a new flagship project climate-proofing the city centre through greening of open spaces and grey infrastructure.

Another example of changing governance within the City of Genk comprised a **recognition of the need to increase the capacity of the Stiemervallei delivery team** within the City Authority. This recognition has been reflected in expanded recruitment in the nature-based solution delivery team to work both within and beyond the Stiemervallei programme.

Financing and business models

City financing innovation included a focus on **pooling regular resources within the space sector** (e.g. nature management, bicycle connections, roads and water-related investments). The different sources of funding secured range between 23.000 € and 2 mil €; in total, so far, there is 2.9 mil € funding secured by pooling regular sources, 3 mil € expected.

In addition to securing the financing for delivery of the four spatial transformation projects, the successful grant capture at a Flemish level for operationalisation of the SuDS & Soda sub-project **helped raise awareness of the effectiveness of adopting a nature-based solution approach in funding proposals.** Accessing funding at a regional level has, historically, been viewed as challenging for the City of Genk. Thus, this latest success has led to broad acknowledgement of the value of the nature-based solution approach in funding proposals and is now being mainstreamed across other design/development approaches. The grant received for SUDs & SODA can indeed be considered as an innovation and breakthrough, because a traditional funding mechanism for sewage infrastructure has been opened up; a new category for experimenting with NBS was added under pressure of 2 Flemish cities (one of them being Genk).

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Nature-based Enterprises

Connecting Stiemer nature with **entrepreneurship** was a goal of the project team. In part, this was achieved by using the Stiemer Deals as a catalyst for economic development and entrepreneurship. However, a key aspect to delivery on this ambition will not be realised until the Stiemer sub-projects are more fully realised, and the attractiveness of the valley can be used as both a stimulus and a foundation for business, including nature-based enterprises.

Co-production

A **professional communication strategy** and recognisable visual language were established to reach and involve stakeholders. This was based on a process of creating visibility and pride, promoting engagement through education and co-creation, and then driving active participation.

The community engagement and communication strategy for the Stiemervallei programme are underpinned by the Friends of the Stiemer programme and Stiemer Deals. The **Stiemer Deals programme adopted an entirely novel social innovation approach for the city**: a voluntary agreement between the City of Genk and other partners from across the city (other city services, citizens, organizations, companies) in relation to delivering mutually aligned ambitions associated with the Stiemervallei. This goes beyond co-production to innovative co-governance and co-financing for the stewardship phase. Officially launched in 2020, this innovative policy instrument is now integral to creating ecological, economic and social value from the Stiemervallei programme, delivering such innovations as Stiemer ice cream and Stiemer beer.

Co-production activities ranged from the traditional to the more creative, including bicycle tours, neighbourhood dialogues, Stiemer quizzes, and the engagement of a Junior Team of local school children as child ambassadors.

Social Innovation approaches developed through the Stiemervallei programme have also been expanded to include the City's New Energy Project.

Impact Assessment

A suite of environmental, social, and economic indicators have been implemented to establish a baseline for monitoring impact from the Stiemervallei programme as it rolls out. This has included engaging with a citizen-science-based Stiemerlab project that is monitoring the water quality of the Stiemer waterway. This will be **used as a baseline for assessing change** and there are discussions about broadening this approach to include monitoring SuDS & Soda. In addition, a Social/Health and Wellbeing survey has been carried out in the Stiemervallei catchment which will be repeated regularly to capture a measure of social change.

Reflexive Monitoring

A **Stiemer diary process** was implemented for all members of the Stiemer team to journal day-to-day activities. Explored as a team in monthly reflection sessions, the journals formed the basis for understanding the barriers and charting the successes of the Stiemer programme delivery.

Following the successful implementation of the reflexive monitoring process on the Stiemer governance process, reflexive monitoring has now been **transferred to the development of other major programmes** within the City Authority

Technical Solutions

To build SuDS into the exemplar in Genk, it was necessary to take a step backwards and **explore how to build engagement and capacity for SuDS** more fundamentally in the region. This is being achieved through the nature-based solution SuDS engagement and demonstrator as part of the SuDS & Soda project.

Bringing a co-creative approach into tendering procedure enables the combining of different departmental goals into the Technical design.

Building relations to **break through silo thinking and overcome system boundaries** in external organisations can unlock more multifunctional NBS design and financing. Bringing cities authorities together to influence this can bring more pressure to this than individual administrations.

Failed funding proposals can represent a step forward in implementation if they **act as a catalyst for multidisciplinary design collaboration**.

Recognition for the value of an NBS team and an NBS project can equate to **recognition for a nature-based solution approach more broadly**, particularly in relation to how they engage with their colleagues.

Governance

City-wide Thematic Working Group meetings are valuable for facilitating discussions with responsible actors in relation to 'safe-guarding' the vision of the masterplan during project development. They can also **create new working dynamics**, creating direct collaborations with external partners that would previously have been managed by another City Authority department.

Collaboration with existing partners on new NBS approaches can create new symbiotic relationships, and can simplify procurement processes if collaboration covers different phases of planning and delivery.

By **changing the way of working into a co-productive way, a collaborative governance model is created that can bridge communication gaps**. This can be particularly beneficial when seeking innovative solutions for tendering NBS.

Having **a narrative that relates to wider city and Sustainable Development Goal strategies helps embed NBS approaches into policy plans** by, for example, convincing decision-makers of the project's significance and herewith creating new relations. This increased support leads to a new discourse around the project's significance and the implementation and scaling of NBS.

Budgeting processes can have unwritten rules and important power relations that are challenging to navigate. It can be beneficial to form alliances with senior decision-makers to help navigate this.

Taking ownership for policy plan actions can be an effective mechanism for ensuring that NBS becomes embedded at a higher governance level.

The **Stiemer Deals are an effective mechanism for unlocking 'dormant' capacity but require a novel way of governing by the city team** (e.g. with regards to the contact point and facilitating the network) and collaboration with the purchasing department.

When trying to drive change in local entrepreneurship around NBS, **actors to facilitate change embedded locally allows long-term relationships to develop**.

Replication of the governance model to other sectors can provide insights into generic elements of a governance model.

Working with **a tailored communication strategy** enables connecting activities to communication in a very initiative way, improving project governance

Financing and business models

There is a need to **embed NBS into the City's economics department**. To do this, there is a need for capacity in terms of nature-based economy expertise and knowledge.

New policy plans bring new financing challenges, but it can help to open up new funding opportunities.

Collaborations developed, even during failed funding proposals, can create opportunities for new funding sources

Building a strong narrative to embed an NBS programme into city policy plans can represent a pathway for securing financing.

Preparing a **clear budget with detailed plans** can make it easier for influential advocates to back a proposal for city funding.

Embedding NBS programmes in policy plans can secure city budget as match-funding for external funds.

When working on tenders/applications that ask for complex solutions, **fitting proposals into the system of the tender/application can represent a barrier**.

Citizen-orientated NBS public-private partnerships, can represent an effective financing approach.

Nature-based Enterprises

Stimulation of entrepreneurship opportunities is an effective driver for securing NBS financing as part of regeneration processes.

Nature-based enterprise creation, incubation, and acceleration is a unique challenge requiring sector specific understanding. This can be challenging for a city NBS team without such expertise.

Co-production

Including co-production processes with other departments into the preparation of tendering processes can help overcome gaps between vision and implementation.

Co-production activities with external strategic actors can be an effective way of increasing delivery capacity by up-skilling partners to deliver their own projects independently.

Knowledge collected in co-production processes can increase knowledge and capacity of community groups.

'Clean-up' campaigns can represent a gateway for wider engagement.

Mapping and contacting local stakeholders based on spatial location, combined with mapping the social fabric of the area, can build a sense of belonging through the campaign.

External organisations can help to build bridges between communities and the city team.

Stiemer Deals proved to be a very effective co-production innovation for engaging actors and raising awareness.

Co-producing a purchasing strategy with volunteers from non-government organisations can represent a barrier if volunteers are reluctant to take responsibility, particularly if there is a lack of clarity in relation to the role.

Being locally embedded is important in relation to co-producing entrepreneurship due to the importance of the role of place.

Building relationships with partners and citizens via informal, 'fun' activities strengthens more instrumental co-production initiatives.

Including citizens (Friends of the Stiemer) **in soundboard meetings with experts** increases the awareness of experts for the impact on citizens and increases the commitment of the Friends of the Stiemer

Impact Assessment

Implementing a new policy plan also creates a need for new indicators to monitor its process.

Implementing indicators does not need to mean entirely new processes and resources. It can be possible to utilise and/or supplement existing data generation processes.

Reflexive Monitoring

The reflexive monitoring process has been one of the main success factors for the Genk Stiemer exemplar. A lot of effort was put into **integrating the learning process into the overall governance and implementation strategy of the exemplar**. A key insight has been the realisation that reflexive monitoring is a process that runs parallel to the regular project management, but at the same time is sufficiently interlinked.

Many of the learning outcomes of the learning process have a relevance that exceeds the Stiemer programme. **Many barriers sit at organisational level of the municipality**. The Stiemer programme offers great opportunities for organisational learning.

The learning process ensures that the right things are done while the project management ensures that the things are done right. With the Stiemer programme, it is one of the first times for our urban transformation processes that we have succeeded to bridge the essential but very often missing link between the strategic ambitions of the city of Genk and the plethora of actions that are undertaken.

4. Glasgow

Nature-based solutions implementation process

Glasgow's narrative

Glasgow exemplar: the Open Space Strategy

Description: The Open Space Strategy is a city wide resource to help address the changing demands on its open space caused by biodiversity loss, anthropogenic demand, and climate change. The Strategy is being used to consider the different ways in which the people, flora, and fauna of Glasgow will need to make use of open space, now and in the future. By adopting a nature-based solution approach to this challenge, these demands are considered in a transdisciplinary way in relation to how open spaces are funded, managed, and created to deliver multifunctional environmental, social, and economic benefits.

Societal challenges addressed:

- Green networks delivering greater positive outcomes such as biodiversity, jobs, safety, physical and mental health.
- Increased local stakeholder-led engagement and entrepreneurship in relation to open spaces.
- Greater financial investment in green/blue water management solutions and greater recognition of the value of urban water as a resource.
- Positive secondary impacts (co-benefits) such as safer streets and public spaces, physical and mental health has been improved.

Figure 3. Glasgow's framework figure

The diagram illustrates the project's three distinct phases and the infinity loop links each phase and that they can also be in progress simultaneously – this is definitely the case for the Glasgow project. The first phase predates most of Glasgow's current team and much of that knowledge has been passed on by colleagues. This section tells the story of Glasgow's exemplar through the key transformation points during and through Connecting Nature. The overarching theme is about place and how decisions influence what is going on, on the ground and affecting open spaces in localized places across the city and citizens' lived experiences.

The first point of transformation to getting the strategy adopted was embedding a place-based approach with a nature based solutions lens within policy. By embedding the importance of the environment and NBS within policies the Glasgow team got more traction and resources were moved to develop the Strategy.

The next point of transformation was getting a fully staffed Connecting Nature team and especially managing to hire a GIS specialist. This has been key to progress on the project and has meant that the team could begin identifying the relevant data and indicators for the development of the Delivery Plan Map. As seen on the figure, the red dot in the Planning phase is the largest and this is due to the importance of the early data collection that was done after hiring the specialist. As a team they were able to start identifying social, environmental, and economic data and indicators and to start developing the dashboard. During the development of the dashboard the team realised that the exemplar is at city scale and that it would be useful to have some smaller projects they could use as pilots to test some of the early learnings and indicators. The projects identified are an important factor in all three phases of the framework.

The next transformation point of the framework is the adoption of the Open Space Strategy. When the Council formally adopted the Open Space Strategy the document became a public document and a key consideration for any development of Glasgow's protected open spaces. This allowed the team to clearly and confidently move into the delivery phase. The overarching theme here is implementing the plans and proposal to create the delivery map exemplar.

The fifth point of transformation was when they were able to properly adapt and embed Reflexive Monitoring into the delivery process. This was done by reaching out across teams and services to ensure they had regular contact with the key people to help deliver the exemplar. This process has allowed the team to record critical turning points and work towards collaborative ways to overcome issues. It has also had a positive effect on governance because it has allowed communication between teams at an officer level at least where an agreed governance structure at senior management has not yet been achieved. This has allowed us to make positive relationships with relevant colleagues and continue to make progress.

The sixth point of transformation was when being able to apply co-production methods via demonstrators projects like Growchapel where they undertook the Business Model Canvas activity which allowed them to work with project partners and members of the community to take forward key project development actions. They also carried out a number of stakeholder mapping workshops with partners at Green Space Scotland. This meant they could identify key stakeholders in local areas for future engagement, locate and learn from NBS projects on the ground, and also raise the public profile of Connecting Nature in Glasgow.

The seventh point of change was when they started having conversations about finance and business modelling associated with the Open Space Strategy Development Plan. The team being fully staffed allowed this to happen and it meant they could start making progress on another dimension of the Open Space Strategy (OSS).

Of course, impact assessment continues all the way through because our exemplar is data-driven – this is because it is one of the key framework elements. Impact assessment will be particularly important when the team can start to measure the success of the delivery plan across different scales.

The Glasgow team have started working on elements of the stewardship phase by developing a strategy for nature-based entrepreneurship and working on ways to better utilize private investment. Their nature-based accelerator programme has just been launched with a main aim of supporting nature-based enterprise ideas that have a positive impact in terms of helping to achieve the objectives of the OSS and helping to steward their open spaces and at the same time as creating a local nature-based economy for the city. They are also reviewing our developer contributions policy so they can ensure monies collected via development can be better targeted at all open space uses.

As part of the dissemination process within Connecting Nature each of the front runner cities are hosting a Connecting Nature Summit. The Leader of the Council launched the series on 23rd to 25th March with the Connecting Nature Innovation Summit in Glasgow. The virtual event attracted over 1200 registrations from 70+ countries. Over 850 people actively participated in at least one of the webinars and innovation café sessions. The summit considerably raised the profile of the Connecting Project in Glasgow and Glasgow's exemplar work.

'Connecting Nature work is helping bring this together and is putting an **NBS approach** on the map in Glasgow and Scotland – the success of the summit demonstrates this.'

Mainstreaming figure

Figure 4. Glasgow's transformation pathway for mainstreaming nature-based solutions. A self-reflection by the city CN team in relation to their transformation during the Connecting Nature project.

Actions

Development of the Open Space Strategy, and follow up activities that are securing its rollout across the city, have been delivered through diverse transformational activities aligned with the elements of the Connecting Nature NBS Framework: Technical Solutions; Governance; Financing and business models; Nature-based enterprises; Co-production, Impact Assessment, and Reflexive Monitoring.

Technical Solutions

The Open Space Strategy NBS exemplar has been developed, peer-reviewed, and adopted by the council. It is now shaping urban planning and development activities across the city, **using nature positive approaches to enhance the environmental, social and economic value of its open spaces.**

An Open Space Quality Assessment was developed and carried out on all amenity greenspace, parks and public gardens and other open space types that can have multiple uses and are >0.3ha across the city. This provides **a foundation for understanding both the current state of open spaces and the future potential.**

A Connecting Nature spatial database was developed to map the social, economic, and environmental context across Glasgow. The Open Space Quality Assessment was included in the database which is now being used as a **tool for understanding the local context needs when planning optimal nature-based solutions design, delivery, and stewardship.** The tool is being used across departments/themes including the Development Plan, playspace revitalisation, urban agriculture, water management, and the Woodland Strategy.

Building from the spatial database development, Glasgow City Council (GCC) is partnering with NatureScot, the Scottish Government, and Dark Matters Labs to develop TreesAI: an open-source platform to map, value and finance urban forests. This will underpin **better decision-making in relation to tree planting, management, and stewardship.** The project will be piloted at COP26 and will subsequently represent a funding stream for mainstreaming nature-based solutions across the city.

The Open Space Strategy is also being rolled out incrementally through individual projects. For example, the Growchapel community garden – a **co-created community allotment facility recently launched in the city to promote social interaction within the community and with nature,** healthy eating, outdoor activity and other health and wellbeing impacts.

Governance

Innovation actions in relation to governance focused on developing an interdepartmental approach for the Open Space Strategy to provide **a framework for collaboration and co-financing across the city council and externally.**

The Open Space Strategy has contributed to the **restructuring of the Sustainability and Planning departments to align them with the Development Plan group.** Also, with the declaration of a Climate Emergency and Ecological Emergency by the council.

A Climate Plan was developed alongside the Corporate Climate Liaison Group. Both of which were co-led by the Glasgow Connecting Nature team lead.

An additional governance action was the production of an Elected Members Briefing on nature-based solutions, developed jointly with COSLA, The Improvement Service, and Nature Scot.

The Scottish UrbanByNature Hub also represents a governance action in development. The Hub will **drive knowledge exchange and build capacity in relation to nature-based solution implementation.** The Glasgow Connecting Nature team engaged several stakeholder organisations including statutory nature, environment, and planning organisations, and local authority network representatives, to co-create this strategic knowledge exchange platform.

The Connecting Nature Framework was used as a tool to review and then relaunch the Strategic Stalled Spaces programme that has been running in Glasgow for the last 10 years. It **identified the need to provide more support to communities** around the key areas identified within the framework and that project identification, mapping and signposting were critical. This opened discussions with Community Land Scotland around community ownership, and the Scottish Land Commission. It was also used to leverage £150k of Vacant and Derelict Land funding in Drumchapel.

Financing and business models

A key focus of the Corporate Climate Liaison Group was **exploring the finances necessary to deliver the Climate Plan.** Resources are coming through the climate plan to the Sustainability team that will be used to deliver on the Open Space Strategy.

Work is ongoing to **secure resources for roles extending beyond the duration of the Connecting Nature** project for delivering the Open Space Strategy and nature-based solutions.

As proof of concept for the Open Space Strategy approach, **£500K has been secured from the Scottish Government through Parks & Operation Department to deliver and update playspaces across the city.** The project will be developed as a pilot for the Open Space Strategy approach, with the intention that this will be mainstreamed for the subsequent £5m that the Scottish Government will be investing in open space improvements. The Parks & Operation department are collaborating with the Connecting Nature team by using the NBS spatial dataset to better understand locations with the potential to deliver the greatest benefits to local communities, and the co-benefits that can be delivered through nature-based solution approaches.

Trees AI represents a public-private funded collaboration to develop **a tool for scaling private sector investment in urban nature-based solutions** in Glasgow. The tool uses an intelligent system of understanding and valuing carbon credits and ecosystem service provision to unlock delivery and stewardship funding.

£150k has been allocated from the Scottish Government financed Vacant and Derelict Land (VDL) fund to use Nature Based Solutions to unlock the development of VDL in Drumchapel. This has been built on the use of Open Space Strategy data, and is being used as a pilot for upscaling.

Co-production

Co-production was delivered at two levels. Firstly, at strategic level in relation to the Open Space Strategy. For this, **co-production was used as a method to engage with various stakeholders at multiple levels of the process** of developing and implementing the Open Space Strategy.

Open Space Strategy co-production included **public consultation using a blend of innovative approaches for the council** including online questionnaires, public exhibitions, and key questions on postcards distributed through the city's Library and Council Office network.

Secondly, **co-production was focused on a nature-based solution strategic pilot project level, demonstrating the rollout potential of the Open Space Strategy.** This included co-production workshops as part of the development of Growchapel (including applying the Nature Based Solutions Business Model Canvas method), the redevelopment of the Burrell Museum in Pollok Park, and the next iteration of the city's Stalled Spaces programme to include a greater focus on nature-based solutions.

Co-production approaches were also used for the development of the new Food Growing Strategy. The Nature Based Solutions Business Model Canvas was used as the catalyst for this, **creating a narrative around which potential social, environmental, health and economic benefits could be better articulated and realised.**

Co-production approaches have led to the co-development of Every Tree Tells a Story: a social cohesion and lived experience NBS project to capture and map tree stories across the city. Co-designed with Strathclyde University and GCC Education Improvement Service, it seeks to **empower communities to use creativity to capture stories about the trees and the spaces in which they sit.**

The co-production skills developed by the Connecting Nature team have also allowed them to support and partner in the Hidden Environmental Histories of the Clyde project.

Reflexive Monitoring

Reflexive Monitoring methodologies were adopted and adapted by the Glasgow Connecting Nature team to support the development and implementation of the Open Space Strategy.

Key learning outcomes from the Reflexive Monitoring process included recognition of the **value of developing a business model canvas to improve communication to colleagues** in relation to exploring and communicating the nature-based solution exemplar aims.

Reflexive Monitoring also **raised awareness of the barriers related to Glasgow City Council procurement and recruitment practices** when developing nature-based solutions.

Reflexive Monitoring methods were adapted by the Glasgow Connecting Nature team in order to simplify the process. This further **encouraged the participation of key colleagues in different services and helped to reduce silo-working practices.**

Nature-based Enterprises

The initiating action for nature-based enterprises was to **map the current innovation ecosystem** and to consider where innovation in nature-based entrepreneurship/enterprise (NBE) might fit.

Following this, Glasgow City Council partnered with The Melting Pot's Good Ideas and Glasgow Caledonian University in **establishing to an NBE accelerator pilot programme to support early-stage nature-based businesses,** with a view to developing a nature-based economy around NBS stewardship and use. With 40 quality applications for the initial 10 places, the programme was heavily oversubscribed. Due to this demand, enrolment was increased to 15 high potential start-ups, all of which undertook the accelerator programme, graduating in September 2021. Following this success, there are now plans to develop this programme further.

Impact Assessment

The Glasgow Connecting Nature team have worked to develop a suite of indicators to evaluate the impact of nature-based solutions at both a city level (to monitor the incremental impact of the open space strategy) and at a local level (to monitor the impact of individual nature-based solution pilots). Research was undertaken in the summer of 2019, to identify potential data sources for the indicators and to build a baseline for the City of Glasgow. This led to **new interdepartmental collaborations across Glasgow City Council and external collaboration with partners** including the National Health Service Greater Glasgow and Clyde, the Biological Record Centre, Glasgow Caledonian University, and the Scottish Government. For some indicators, it was not possible to identify a partner able to supply the data. For these, it was necessary to implement new evaluation processes, some of which are expected to be picked up following the end of this Horizon 2020 project.

In parallel to the indicator development, a dashboard was created as a way to map and represent some of the existing baseline of health, social, environmental and economic trends across the city. The aim being to provide a baseline for comparison of the future outcomes of the City's Open Space Strategy and the impacts of NBS implementation across the city. The dashboard allows viewers to visualize the interplay of different indicators (e.g. health status, social deprivation, greenspace distribution) in a particular city location. As such, it is a useful instrument for identifying types of indicators and data that might be missing, thus orienting future impact assessment decisions. It is also **valuable in terms of informing strategic planning of nature-based solution design and management, in order to meet local needs.**

The development of the suite of indicators has **supported knowledge sharing with the local universities** and has allowed co-production of a Research Council bid called Gallant.

Connecting Nature brought in a Geographical Information Systems (GIS) officer to support this evaluation impact indicator and dashboard development, and to implement a programme of evaluation on the exemplar rollout. Work is ongoing to secure the legacy of this GIS position to **ensure continuity of the spatial analysis and impact** evaluation components of the Open Space Strategy through the Glasgow City Dashboard.

Working with Connecting Nature partners, Glasgow City Council also **co-developed an interactive evaluation impact planning tool** (Co-Impact). A prototype of the tool has been developed and tested, and a version for launch is underdevelopment. The tool supports users in identifying appropriate indicators for impact evaluation and provides links to appropriate metrics for implementing these.

Development has begun on a **Scottish UrbanByNature Hub**. This will include a focus on impact assessment to align with the Scottish Government priorities in relation to Digital Planning and Data.

Technical Solutions

Site visits are a very effective mechanism for evaluating the topography, constraints, access, etc, when planning nature-based solutions. However, they also have a greater value: **site visits can be an effective mechanism for strengthening relationships with, and learning about projects from, colleagues from other departments.** Such face-to-face conversations provide opportunity for more informal conversations that can strengthen collaboration between colleagues from different departments.

Strategically, **using high-level initiatives such as COP26 and the Climate Emergency announcements can be an effective way to increase awareness** around the multi-functional benefits of nature-based solutions.

Technical demonstrators are also an effective way to raise the profile of nature-based solutions by demonstrating what can be achieved in a local context.

Another effective mechanism for engaging others in Technical Solution delivery was aligning with the National Park City campaign. The campaign involved **a network of delivery actors who represented key contacts for nature-based solution delivery.**

Governance

There was **a lack of consistent, established, and agreed internal cross-service governance structure at management/senior management level.** A novel Open Space team meeting was established to address this. The meeting comprised key officers at operational management level focused across the 15 themes of the Open Space Strategy. The meeting formalised what was previously an informal networking process.

Collaboration for the Nature-Based Enterprise accelerator programme represented governance innovation for the City Council Connecting Nature team as it partnered with the Centre for Civic Innovation and utilised their networks.

A shift towards co-productive model working with 'Friends of' groups represented a governance shift in relation to delivery. Out-sourcing delivery and providing support in the form of capacity building resources, represented a new way of working.

Delivery of the Open Space Strategy also required **new ways of governing how the council managed their assets across departments.** Property Sales, in particular, required the creation of new relations (less formal, better working relationships) between the departments at strategic levels and new practices for collaboration.

Story mapping methodology was used to showcase funding opportunities, to share learning, and as an engagement tool. **Visually representing nature-based solution concepts helped underpin discussions with other policy makers.**

The focus **on using the Open Space Strategy to inform the development of outdoor play and learning spaces also represented governance innovation for the city,** due to the cross-departmental collaboration and support processes.

The **Glasgow Summit has partly led to the team being more easily able to improve and work on governance structures** because of the senior management involvement and elected official support (for the summit and then subsequently firmed up for the project as a whole too).

Financing and business models

The Open Space Strategy provides a **mechanism for combining departmental budgets under the new governance structure.** This facilitates easier access to multiple budgets and better value for money across budgets.

Capacity-building of community groups also included a focus on financing to support out-scaling of nature-based solution delivery beyond the Glasgow Connecting Nature team. This focused on unlocking different kinds of funding that would not be accessible to the council.

Participation as hosts of COP26 has brought much focus on Glasgow and has **presented broader opportunities in relation to pilot/proof-of-concept financing.** Similarly, participation in the National Park City campaign has opened additional new funding opportunities.

Story mapping was an **effective mechanism for showcasing funding opportunities.**

Going forward, the team hopes the elevation of the project's profile through the Glasgow Summit and the positive feedback and legacy from **the summit could help with pulling in more finance for open space projects.** Particularly as we were able to present our Growchapel demonstrator, albeit virtually which demonstrated how we applied co-production tools such as the business model canvas and have tried to leverage and maximise funding opportunities.

Nature-based Enterprises

The **Open Space Strategy provided an effective framework for generating a nature-based economy** around nature-based solution planning, delivery, and stewardship.

The **Nature-Based Enterprise accelerator programme was an effective mechanism for knowledge transfer** to nature-based enterprises in relation to how enterprises could source funding and what sort of business modelling they could adopt.

The Nature-Based Enterprise accelerator programme partners have recently been awarded research resource from a Glasgow School of Art research team to carry out a systems-led review of the pilot. The aim of this is to assess the progress of the Nature-Based Academy participants as well **help to begin to forge a local Nature-Based Enterprise ecosystem in Glasgow.**

COP26 networks provided connections to multiple nature-based enterprises.

A novel **collaboration with the nature-based enterprise - Urban Good - expanded the Open Space Strategy to more layers**, e.g. showing uses of open space. Urban Good also produced offline paper maps, making them accessible to different audiences.

Co-production

A **co-production approach was effective for producing the teaching programme for the Nature-Based Enterprise accelerator.** This was done through collaboration with the Glasgow Connecting Nature team and local partners.

Learning from the way communities organised themselves during COVID around local challenges provided important lessons in terms of the need for Nature-Based Solutions in specific areas.

The pandemic did not mean an end to co-production with 'Friends of' groups. Instead, it represented a new way of establishing these community groups. **Virtual and hybrid approaches were effective, and sometimes meant greater engagement.** It also led to the creation of videos for supporting capacity building which were a more sustainable legacy compared to one-off workshops.

Co-production processes can provide a valuable source of knowledge/data when mapping local environmental, social, and economic context.

Steering committee approaches to pilot project delivery with community representatives on the committees was an effective foundation for facilitating co-production processes with local stakeholders.

The **Glasgow Summit also made it easier to work on the team's entrepreneurship strategy.** For example, setting up the partnership and attracting participants for the nature-based accelerator was easier partly because partners became aware of Connecting Nature by attending the summit earlier in the year and so were keen to work with the team.

Impact Assessment

If carried out at a city scale, the value of impact assessment extends beyond just evidencing the impact of a nature-based solution pilot. **By bringing disparate datasets together into a central resource it is possible to also support more integrated and targeted decision-making** for Nature-Based Solution planning by promoting data sharing and interdepartmental working.

In addition to city-scale indicators, **local scale evaluation of pilots can be used to raise the profile of central strategy**, enhancing the ability to continue Nature-Based Solution delivery beyond the Horizon 2020 project funding.

Moving from informal evaluation to formal evaluation helps to mainstream Nature-Based Solution implementation from one driven by anecdotal evidence to a robust science-based approach based on robust data.

Reflexive Monitoring

The structure of the Open Space meeting was inspired by the Reflexive Monitoring process, the learnings sessions, how the team internally discussed the tracker, and how they prepared for the reflexive monitoring meetings.

The Glasgow team discovered that it was best to simplify the Reflexive Monitoring process when carrying out these meetings. They **identified a team member to undertake each Reflexive Monitoring role** and to undertake the tracker updates and structured notes post-meeting, to avoid complicating the process for colleagues who only engaged with matters on an ad-hoc basis. The Connecting Nature team also found it valuable to discuss how the process worked with other colleagues who expressed an interest in adopting Reflexive Monitoring as a method for use in other projects.

5. Poznań Nature-based solutions implementation process

Poznan's narrative

Poznań exemplar: Network of small-scale nature-based solutions

Description: Designed around a green wedge system, Poznań is a city rich in green spaces. Despite the green wedges penetrating deep into the city, dense built-up districts in the historical areas lack biodiversity exacerbating key challenges such as pollution, flooding, heat stress and extreme cold. The exemplar is the out-scaling of pocket parks and urban gardens to improve equitable access to nature in very urbanised areas and those with higher population densities, to address these key challenges. Exemplar delivery has focused on a series of eco- and social-gardens at kindergartens across the city.

Societal challenges addressed:

- Climate Change adaptation (relief from thermal stress, more permeable spaces better at managing rainfall)
- Increasing biodiversity and the human connection to this nature.
- Educational benefits
- Improved air quality
- Active play and relaxation spaces
- Raising the profile of the value of a nature-based solution approach to urban design.

Figure 5. Poznan's framework figure

Poznan's framework figure uses the transformation points to tell the story of the specific exemplar – implementation of nature-oriented playgrounds, while some of these points are seen as ongoing processes. For each transformation point/process, a reflection illustrates the changes, benefits and difficulties during Connecting Nature's three phases: planning, delivery and stewardship.

Poznan's work on the diagram allowed for an in-depth diagnosis and identification of the significant key transformation points that appeared during and through the Connecting Nature project, changing the manner of working among the Poznan team. First of all is the education aspect in general: ecological education, education about NBS among stakeholders, partners, policy-makers as well as entrepreneurs; also increasing knowledge about Nature-Based Enterprise Strategy and Summit in Poznan. On every stage of the process is the crucial point and it's significance to spreading the knowledge and awareness about nature-based solutions in the city.

Another transformation point is the monitoring and impact assessment as well as developing indicators – mainly linked to phases of delivery and stewardship. Poznan team considers that internal project evaluation and assessment is important and help to measure the impact and benefits as well as the effectiveness of actions. Poznan evaluates its activities and plans for the future in accordance with the received and developed evidence-based procedures. The Poznan team focuses much more on co-production process, which is substantial part of planning and delivery stage. The more one understands about each stakeholder, the more effectively they can be engaged in the process. Poznan team considers that co-production plays a relevant role in the planning of directions and development as well as managing the process. Co-production can help build stronger communities and develop citizenship.

Furthermore, openness and promotion were found to be important at planning and delivery stages, considered as information cycles about projects and activities in the city. These issues are key points to share the knowledge and ideas of nature-based solutions.

Finally, reflexive monitoring at delivery and stewardship phase: the process helps to break through barriers the organisation comes up against, gives strategic overview of the situation, analyses gaps and identifies resources and activities to fill them. Poznan found it a useful tool to manage projects concerning the implementation of large-scale nature-based solutions in city as the reflexive monitoring scheme gives a broader picture both for the topic of NBS and the scope of the organization.

On the figure, Poznan have identified their trademarks as co-production, NBS education, monitoring and impact assessment. As was mentioned, these three aspects have changed since the beginning of the project and affected the way of working and operationing of the Poznan CN team:

A. Co-production process – considered as activities of cross-sectoral character and of engaging different groups of partners. According to the Poznan team, co-production can help ensure that resources and contribution of different types of knowledge are used to develop the services that citizens really want.

B. Education about nature-based-solutions is a Poznan “trademark” – thanks to the CN project, as well as numerous workshops, there is a visible change in the perception and understanding of NBS in the city, especially among decision-makers and officials.

C. Monitoring and Impact assessment – carry out an evaluation, monitoring results, measuring the impact and benefits of the projects show the effectiveness and indicates the scope for further actions in the city. Collecting data and developing performance indicators for the implemented activities is significant and it should be treated as an integral and relevant part of the project.

Mainstreaming figure

Figure 6. Poznań’s transformation pathway for mainstreaming nature-based solutions. A self-reflection by the city CN team in relation to their transformation during the Connecting Nature project.

Actions

The nature-based solutions exemplar programme is coordinated by the Project Coordination and Urban Regeneration Office of Poznań City Hall. Delivery of the NBS exemplar ecogardens (eco-demonstrators), natural playgrounds as well as floating gardens is well advanced through diverse transformational activities aligned with the elements of the Connecting Nature NBS Framework: Technical Solutions; Governance; Financing and business models; Nature-based enterprises; Co-production, Impact Assessment, and Reflexive Monitoring.

Technical Solutions

Technical Solutions - has focused on the multifunctional design of the NBS exemplars to balance trade-offs in relation to delivering local benefits (based on the immediate needs of the users and locality) and broader benefits (based on key strategic needs of the city). This has included a design focus on the creation of aesthetics balanced with functional spaces that attract a high degree of activity, daily interactions, and social gatherings. A series of different nature-based solution spaces have been delivered across the city:

Current status of spatial transformation projects –

Eco-demonstrators – are elements made of natural materials (plant, wood) representing ecological and environmental phenomena. For example: insect houses, garden wooden pots/flower beds filled with compost soil for planting, live willow huts, numerous climbers (plants) or fruit bushes. Education class scenarios were also prepared, to be used by teachers in conducting ecological education classes with the use of eco-demonstrators installed in preschool gardens. These nature-based solutions have been successfully out-scaled since the start of Connecting Nature. Overall, at least ten pre-schools have received eco-demonstrators in their playspaces each year since 2018. In total, there are now 46 pre-schools with eco-demonstrators.

Natural playgrounds - the nature oriented-playgrounds are unique places created for pre-school children, where alongside the play equipment you will find elements of nature. This includes sandy hills, live willow huts, and paths made from logs and stumps. These are supplemented with green flowerbeds, fruit bushes, and houses that allow children to grow their own plants or observe insects. These "play gardens" are more than just a playground, giving children and their guardians the opportunity to experience nature directly, and creating additional accessible greenspace in the city. As part of the Connecting Nature project, three nature-oriented playgrounds were created in gardens of nursery schools No. 42, No. 46 and No. 87 in 2017-2018. since this initial success, a total of twenty-one nature-oriented playgrounds have now been installed in Poznań kindergartens.

Floating gardens - in partnership with the OnWater Foundation, five floating gardens have been completed in Poznań (two on Cybina River, three on ponds in parks in Poznań). The floating gardens improve the river/water ecosystem, introducing more biodiversity into the city by providing shelter, feeding, and breeding opportunities. The vegetation cover on them is predominantly native species, supporting local biodiversity targets, but with the potential for additional colonisation. The gardens also impact on water quality by providing a filtration/water purification function.

Open gardens – One of the pre-Connecting Nature actions: the Open Garden at Kindergarten No. 42 in Wilda was a pilot project implemented by the Project Coordination and Urban Regeneration Office in cooperation with Kindergarten No. 42 and the NGO's (Zieleniak Project) initiative. The aim of the project was to develop a garden which would be opened for both the kindergarten children and also for residents of Wilda District in Poznań. The Open Garden is a combination of the idea of a social garden and a natural playground, open to children and adults, especially those using the kindergarten, the neighbouring nursery and primary school, as well as residents of nearby tenement houses. It is a place where children can experience nature, adults can rest, and people can get actively involved growing plants. The project was initiated in 2017 and the garden was finally opened in March 2018. In the period from April to June 2018, a series of weekend family workshops was held in the garden, engaging the residents and promoting the idea of the open garden. Due to necessity, the garden had to be closed to residents during the COVID19 pandemic. However, this provided space for the team to develop new ideas for open gardens at kindergartens in Poznań. There were some interesting collaborations, but often due to lack of finances, organizational barriers, and a pandemic, it was not possible to open new open gardens in the city. At the time of writing, there is only one open garden at preschool no. 42 in Poznań.

Governance

A focus of governance innovation for the exemplar has been on **identifying, engaging, and facilitating the smooth cooperation and transfer of information between different departments and partners** engaged in the process. Central to this was facilitating a collaborative approach between the Project Coordination and Urban Regeneration Office (design part in the frame of CN), the Department Of Education (managing budget earmarked for investments in kindergartens on the basis of multiannual programme created by Poznań City Council), and the individual kindergarten leads (responsible for applying to the Department of Education for the grant for investment, and choosing the way of designing and maintaining their investments).

Co-governance approaches are being developed with the private sector to increase capacity for delivery and stewardship of natural playgrounds

In order to ensure the engagement of senior decision and policy-makers, it was also **critical to map the expected benefits of the Open and Social Gardens programme onto key city strategies** (Development Strategy for the City of Poznań 2020+; Development Strategy of the Warta River in Poznań; Study of Conditions and Directions of Spatial Development of the City of Poznań Environmental Protection Program for the City of Poznań; Municipal Revitalization Program for the City of Poznań; Plan for Sustainable Development of Public Transport for the City of Poznań for 2014-2025; Plan of Adaptation to Climate Change for the city of Poznań to 2030) to demonstrate how the NBS exemplar would deliver on these.

The "Open Garden" located in densely urbanised district of Wilda represented another governance challenge. In this case, exploring how the attractive greenspaces associated the many public institutions in the city could be expanded for use beyond the "usual users". Governance innovation comprised **a collaborative approach towards partial opening of such spaces to citizens who are usually restricted from coming to their premises**. A balance of openness and flexibility from the public institution and respect for rules of conduct defined by the users was necessary, which was achieved using co-creation approaches.

In parallel to the technical delivery of the natural playgrounds, a series of information activities promoting the idea of natural playgrounds were organised. This included a seminar on "Natural playgrounds in pre-school gardens" at the Poznań International Fair as part of a two-day conference "Education for public space". The workshops included activities in which the directors and teachers of nursery schools tried their hand at designing their own kindergarten natural playgrounds, under the supervision of an expert. These **events were designed to build awareness of, and demand for, nature-based approaches to playspaces** at kindergartens and schools, both at an academic and political level.

This approach has been supplemented with the production of a **locally-contextualised catalogue of NBS** to raise awareness of the approach in Poznań.

Financing and business models

Initial financing **focused on innovation in relation to a hybrid model of financing nature-based solutions** by combining different departmental budgets, with external kindergarten budgets, and with resources from the Connecting Nature project. In order to scale finances to include implementation at primary schools additional EU external funding is being sought.

To continue scaling of nature-based solution approaches it was necessary to expand financing. In order to open up new external funding opportunities, the Connecting Nature team **uses their NBS catalogue to engage civil servants and civil servants and developers**, raising their awareness of the tradition of nature-based solutions in Poznan, and the benefits that can be achieved through such approaches. To exploit diverse funding opportunities, the Connecting Nature team are also exploring cooperative approaches with the private sector through sponsorship-based approach.

Entrepreneurship

The City of Poznań **launched an Entrepreneurship Programme at the Connecting Nature Enterprise Summit**. The programme comprised of two parts with the aim of supporting the rollout, design, and stewardship of their nature-based solution exemplars:

- Education for decision makers;
- Training on good practice for contractors/NBEs.

In addition, technical training materials were produced that could be shared with city and district councillors responsible for making budget decisions on a district level. This is being supplemented with an additional training cycle in relation to animating and maintaining natural playspaces. This approach to engaging entrepreneurship with nature-based solutions is being expanded to include other type of NBS (e.g. Floating gardens or rain gardens).

Co-production

The process of **co-production was not a commonly used method in project work**, especially in public administration institutions, such as city halls. The innovative method had to be learnt. Many of the principles were already implicitly known, but they were not used on a daily basis and as operating practice.

The introduction of open gardens at preschools and other public institutions plays a central role in the place-making process. As such, **cooperation between different stakeholders is a key part of the design process for these green interventions**. Novel co-production processes (based on the Connecting Nature Guidebook principles of initiating, consultation, implementation and a continuous process) were trialled to support collaborative working between the Connecting Nature team, the Education Department, the Kindergarten managers, and the nature-based solution designers. For the 'open gardens' the local community user groups represented an additional stakeholder engaged in the co-production process.

For the novel nature-based solution approach to conserving and broadening participation in the allotment gardens, the organisation 'Go and Sow' were contracted to spearhead this. Their actions included **engaging a broader representation of the community in allotment use through a co-production approach**. Allotments in the city centre are in competition from other types of greenspace which are more open to citizens. The co-production process has been exploring how allotments can be opened up as more accessible greenspace, to ensure that they are protected as a key component of Poznań's green infrastructure, removing any risk of redevelopment as grey infrastructure.

Poznań's approach to navigating the challenges of evaluating impact was addressed through **strong partnership working with Adam Mickiewicz University**. Through this partnership the Poznań Connecting Nature team were able to implement environmental, social, and economic indicators for capturing the multifunctional value of their nature-based solution exemplar:

Environmental impact monitoring focused on aspects including **direct measurement of temperature and humidity combined with an index for evaluating biodiversity net-gain** in the open garden, preschool gardens and pocket parks.

Social indicators represented a unique challenge due to Covid limiting the occupancy of the kindergartens, and therefore the use of the natural playspaces. However, some surveys were able to be conducted among teachers, directors and parents.

Economic indicators were focused on 'value' for money. This has included interviews with contractors and ecosystem service valuation.

Reflexive monitoring

Represented a new method for the Poznań City Connecting Nature team. **Problems and difficulties in different aspects of our work were analysed in team meetings**, but no specific tools were used to monitor them.

Reflexive Monitoring proved to be a useful process for supporting coordination of this complex, multifaceted project. It provided **a mechanism for managing strategic sub-projects, analysing gaps, and identifying resources and activities to address them**. It also provided a strategic overview of the situation within the lead organisation, reflecting the context of exemplar implementation and goal attainment through associated activities of other city units.

Technical Solutions

Learning associated with nature-based solution implementation is incremental.

Lessons learned from the multifunctional development of areas at risk of flood along the River Warta, including the creation of city beaches and recreational facilities at the previously neglected riverside sites provided inspiration for increasing the social and ecological potential of areas of the city centre, including strengthening the 'green wedge' (by consolidation and de-fragmentation of urban green).

Opening **collaborations with different departments has the potential to impact the type of technical solutions that are implemented**, bringing in greater multifunctionality.

Sometimes **what appears to be a setback can become a step forward**: Only securing budget for two playgrounds instead of five ended up being a benefit. It provided an opportunity to deepen and enrich the co-creation process to find more innovative solutions. It also led to a focus on developing other types of playgrounds for older children.

Nature-based solution technical design out-scaling is not a copy and paste approach.

Each time the concept is replicated there needs to be consideration of the local context. For example, older children have different learning and playspace needs that need to be reflected through technical designs.

Challenges like COVID-19 can be used as an opportunity to build capacity when implementation is not possible.

For example, multimedia resources showcasing the eco-demonstrator approach during lockdown represented a technical solution themselves in relation to unlocking broader rollout and ensuring the quality of the approach beyond the Connecting Nature team and project.

Interdepartmental collaboration towards a particular technical design for nature-based solutions **can open up opportunities for collaboration in other contexts and locations.**

Governance

Interdepartmental collaboration has been key to mainstreaming NBS and increasing the human and economic capacity for delivery.

Expanding funding to new sources and departments leads to new relations. By opening up new collaborations with other departments to city districts and inhabitants to also include enterprises it is possible to change a city team's practice, potentially broadening the discourse on how other partners use nature-based solutions.

Looking at a city through a **nature-based solution lens can lead to identifying new typologies and a history of nature-based solution use in urban planning.** This can lead to opportunities to change the discourse around nature-based solutions and open the opportunity or new collaboration.

Scaling-up interventions like the nature-oriented playgrounds requires a novel process to ensure the quality of the intervention and new skills for the team are also scaled.

Identifying 'green' agents across city departments can be an effective method to generate influence beyond the immediate team.

Organisational innovation can be necessary if silos are to be burst. **Breaking open silos can raise awareness in relation to new initiatives that can adopt a nature-based solution approach.**

New legal regulations can be required to facilitate collaboration with commercial enterprises under new governance models. Working with commercial partners can be time-intensive at first but can lead to more-efficient practices and new financing opportunities in the long-run.

Even a **failed funding bid can lead to new collaborative ways of working**, if it is based on a new working model between departments/stakeholder groups.

Looking at your city through a nature-based solution lens can provide opportunities to talk and work with different departments and change the governance of nature-based solutions.

EU projects can provide opportunities to develop new organisational structures and collaborations between departments.

Lobbying politicians can be a useful governance practice for the Poznan team to high-level support for budget decisions.

Once successful pilots have been implemented, **it is possible to change governance structures towards promoting nature-based solutions** among other partners that can bring additional capacity for mainstreaming.

Financing and business models

Complex technical designs can represent a barrier in relation to tenders/applications as it can be difficult to fit design proposals into the tender/application system.

It is possible to **engage commercial enterprises to co-finance public initiatives** through linking civic budgets with corporate responsibility/sponsorship processes.

Linking investment with educational value can be a mechanism for securing financing for nature-based solutions.

Opportunities for sharing funding across departments and with district councils should be explored.

Nature-based Enterprises

Part of scaling nature-based solutions includes scaling the nature-based economy associated with implementation. **Sourcing financing to fund the projects may not be enough if there is not sufficient private sector capacity to design and develop the spaces.** It may also be necessary to stimulate the development of nature-based enterprises to be able to deliver the new market demand.

By **changing the discourse and stimulating others to think about their work in relation to nature-based solutions**, it is possible to create new opportunities for nature-based enterprises.

Co-production

Actor-mapping is a key preliminary step in co-production.

Mainstreaming nature-based solutions needs collaboration with other city hall departments in order to maximise the multifunctionality and unlock the necessary expertise and capacity

Co-production can introduce changes to systems that will lead to the ongoing review, development and delivery of new forms of support. **Co-production therefore benefits from a culture of continuous learning** about what has worked and what has not worked.

When forming collaborations with private sector investment, there needs to be a clear offer for sponsors/businesses to be involved, but also the flexibility to co-create the offer with the schools and potential sponsor.

Co-production is not a one-size-fits-all process. Involving primary school kids in the design, delivery and stewardship of nature-based solutions requires a different co-production process with novel tools (e.g. digital).

Communicating about projects can be used as a catalyst for internal co-production.

Co-production tools developed to increase knowledge/capacity for nature-based solution implementation can also be used as educational resources for schools.

Impact Assessment

Indicators are vital for communicating the effectiveness of nature-based solution processes to colleagues and external stakeholders.

Exploring evaluation already undertaken across city departments, and supplementing this through partnerships with academia is an effective way to implement impact monitoring.

Reflexive Monitoring

The process of reflexive monitoring helped to break through barriers that the organisation encountered by providing a strategic overview of the situation, analysing gaps, and identifying resources and activities to fill them.

Reflexive monitoring was a useful tool for managing scaling-out of nature-based solution project implementation across the city.

Reflexivity helps users to see the broader picture of nature-based solution activities within the organization structure – the reflexive monitoring scheme gives a broader picture, both for the topic of nature-based solutions, and the scope of the organization.

Reflexive monitoring helps to track all the different activities in teamwork. It allows time to reflect on the different collaborations and to make sure the short-term actions are aligned with the long-term goals of projects.

Bringing cities to life, bringing life into cities

Deliverable 11 – Annex 1

Genk Nature-based Solution exemplar Case Study

DOCUMENT PROPERTIES

Nature Document	Deliverable 11 – Annex 1: Genk Nature-based Solution exemplar Case Study
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Task Leader	UEL
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Stiemer Vallei, Genk

Figure 1. Artist impression of the completed Stiemervallei route

Area characterisation:

Genk is situated 80 km from the city of Brussels on the border with the Netherlands. Through the Albert Canal, the city is connected to Antwerp and Liège, which was pivotal in the development of local industries. Until 1988, the coal industry was a very important driver for the city's economy. Of the city's 66,000 population, 54% are of foreign origin from about 107 different nationalities, mostly Italians, Turkish, and Dutch, much of this diversity derives from the legacy of this industry.

Like many cities, Genk faces multifaceted challenges, ranging from securing a sustainable economic future, to building resilience in the face of climate change. This includes needs to:

- Find solutions to increasingly frequent episodes of flooding and stormwater overflow.
- Create new business models that create local jobs.
- Increase the attractiveness and quality of the landscape and local ecosystems to create a desirable location to live and visit.

The Stiemervallei represents an opportunity to deliver a nature-based solution for Genk to support its ambition to increase its attractiveness as a place to live and work, that is connected with nature and the local environment: The Stiemer is a forgotten stream that flows through Genk for about 8 km and is under severe pressure. It originates in Waterschei, from there runs

diagonally through the city, connects to the ponds of De Maten and flows into Diepenbeek into the Demer. On a regional scale, the Stiemervallei is part of De Wijers, a unique wetland area of around 700 ha around the cities of Hasselt and Genk. Parts of the valley have been completely enclosed by buildings over the last sixty years, with other parts of the area hidden and forgotten. The stream itself was straightened and thus largely lost contact with its valley area. Nevertheless, in some places the valley still contains valuable natural elements and large parts are protected as a recognized nature reserve.

Tackling water issues in the valley is crucial. The sewage system of all surrounding neighbourhoods feeds into collectors on both sides of the Stiemer. Even with moderate rainfall, wastewater mixed with rainwater spills into the Stiemer, with a negative impact on people and the environment. The accelerated and massive discharge of uncontaminated rainwater from the valley area also causes flooding and drying out of the valley system.

Figure 2. Stiemervallei project area running through the centre of Genk, connecting many key sites across the city.

Slideshow:

Figure 3. Canalised section of the Stiemer Stream. @ City of Genk

Figure 4. Combined sewage overflow in the Stiemer Stream. @ City of Genk

Figure 5. Stiemer stream and active travel route. Due to the condition of the active travel route, it can be difficult to use at some times of the year. @ City of Genk

Figure 6. A visit of the Slagmolen LIP @ City of Genk

Figure 7. Friends of Stiemer group on a bike ride to visit the site. @ City of Genk

Figure 8. The Stiemer Junior Team meet the press as part of their engagement with the Stiemervallei project. @ City of Genk

Objective:

The Stiemervallei provides great potential to re-imagine the natural quality of a stream valley in an urban context and to balance the ecological, environmental, social and economic benefits of such an approach. The City of Genk has been working to integrate the hidden, fragmented, and constricted water and greenery and transform it into a tangible and perceptible valley on the scale of the entire city. A blue-green lifeline that enhances the quality of life of Genk and the resilience of the city. The development of this valley adapts the city for climate change by utilising the natural stormwater management potential of the large catchment area, making the existing ecosystems more robust. At the same time, the valley forms a logical, spatial link between strategic city sites that can facilitate active travel. The programme is also providing added value in the socio-economic area in terms of promoting well-being, social cohesion, and economic opportunities.

The development of the Stiemervallei had been on the agenda of the city for more than 10 years and, prior to the initiation of the Connecting Nature exemplar, several steps had already been initiated. Under the Stiemervallei Flemish Plan Program (2010) of the Flemish Land Agency, the Schansbroek zones, source area of the Stiemer and Slagmolen, were completely or partially redesigned at the entrance to De Maten. In parallel, there was a growing awareness that there was a need for an integrated vision for the entire area, which was drawn up in the 2016-2019 period in collaboration with the 'Tractebel-Descombes-IMDC' consortium. This master plan represented a strategic toolbox for a step-by-step, spatial transformation of the area in which climate adaptation, biodiversity, recreation, social cohesion and sustainable mobility were important themes. Through the Connecting Nature exemplar, the city has been using the Connecting Nature Framework to develop and mainstream this vision through a nature-based solution lens, then to implement it in legislation and action. The Stiemer programme is being operationalised through a series of ambitious strategic sub-projects, both large and small. The co-creation engagement approach adopted by the City of Genk is enabling the Stiemer nature-based solution vision to be operationalised and scaled internally by the city authority, collaboratively in partnership with externally organisations, and by external organisations independently from the city Connecting Nature team.

Actions:

- Delivery of the Stiemervallei NBS exemplar has begun delivery through diverse transformational activities aligned with the elements of the [Connecting Nature NBS Framework](#): [Technical Solutions](#); [Governance](#); [Financing and business models](#); [Nature-based enterprises](#); [Co-production](#); [Impact Assessment](#); and [Reflexive Monitoring](#).

Technical Solutions:

- Technical Solutions has focused on four transformation projects designed to incrementally deliver the Stiemervallei vision and to engage stakeholders in the broader NBS project ambitions:
 - Current status of spatial transformation projects:
 - *SuDS & Soda* – implementation of this innovative SuDS project is underway. New to the Flemish region, this project is delivering a new

water cycle SuDS experimental approach that includes a focus on entrepreneurship. Implementation of a SuDS Living Lab is beginning Autumn 2021 and will be completed in early 2022. The Living Lab is the first phase of broader SuDS rollout on public and private land. The Living Lab will be used to increase the visibility of SuDS approaches and will lay a foundation for broader rollout in 2023 by introducing the community to the water cycle and the value of SuDS. An external consortium is building this demonstration site which will act as a catalyst for the Water Strategy Masterplan, scaling SuDS approaches in all neighbourhoods around the Stiemervallei. Everything is in place for implementation: the public domain component design is almost ready; the private domain and Living Lab (with new external consortium playing a key role) is ready for delivery. All of these delivery tracks will be up and running in Nov 2021. The overall outcome being using SuDS to prevent stormwater overflow in the catchment of the Stiemervallei. The water company – Aquafin - are financing the installation of the SuDS. As this is a significant shift for them from funding grey to green infrastructure, it is also a key learning/pilot experiment for them at a Flemish regional level.

- *Slagmolen* – this project comprises the redesign of green/blue infrastructure areas of the Slagmolen as part of a flood mitigation and renaturalisation programme. The project area forms the gateway from the City of Genk to the Natura2000 area ‘De Maten’ - a wetland system highly dependent on sufficient and high quality water to support its water-dependent ecosystems. Regular combined sewer overflows from the Stiemerbeek bring poor quality water to this wetland system, threatening its ecological integrity. As part of the Stiemervallei exemplar, design plans have started for Phase 2 of this nature-based solution approach. Co-creation design and planning activities have been undertaken. A delay of 6 months has arisen due to complex hydrology in the project area, revealed by monitoring and recent flooding following implementation of the Phase 1 project. In 2022, preparation for implementation will be carried out with implementation of the nature-based solution approach due to start in Spring 2023.
- *Gardens of Waterschei* – this Stiemervallei transformation project is focused on the creation of a green lung connecting the key city assets of Stalenstraat and Thor Park. The ambition being to stimulate environmental, social and economic for the entrepreneurs of Stalenstraat by restoring a more natural water system, increasing the connection with nature and with other districts surrounding the Stiemerbeek. The first phase of this project has been constructed with a new blue/green terrace pilot intervention now opened. The second phase, the creation of a physical Stiemer Hub is also underway with a 6-month co-design and development programme managed by an external process/co-creation expert. On completion, the Stiemer Hub will provide an experimental environment to catalyse the Stiemervallei’s Stiemer Deals programme, providing a physical space

to enhance the quintuple helix stakeholder interaction. The deadline for the first phase of completion is the end April 2022 with launch of the building overlooking the Stiemer Valley, including surrounding green/blue infrastructure, scheduled for the Genk Innovation Summit.

- *Vallei Route* – an active travel route through the Stiemervallei. This spatial transformation project has a similar timeline to the other projects. Contracted partner Tractebel will develop the technical design, following this, there will be a need to manage the planning and procurement processes, with implementation beginning in spring 2022.

Governance:

- The Stiemervallei project’s organic top-down opportunity-driven approach and bottom-up convergence of small and large projects and visions represented an organizational challenge for the small Environment & Sustainable Development Department within the City of Genk. Initiated as a horizontal working process bridging multidisciplinary consultative bodies in sub-projects, it was necessary to shift to a program-based governance approach, with a clear implementation strategy for integrating the various sub-projects. Instead of the sum of project structures, this required a clear and integrated governance model characterized by a horizontal, co-creative approach in which involvement and ownership are central principles.
- The innovative collaborative governance model developed for the Stiemervallei NBS programme, is now being mainstreamed across other major city programmes (e.g. Energy Sector).

Figure 5. The collaborative governance model developed for the Stiemervallei programme is now being mainstreamed across other city programmes

- Scaled-up greening across the city is now being mainstreamed in the next policy round. Social and ecological benefits of nature-based solution are being increasingly recognised and adopted across the city departments. The exception, perhaps, being economic mainstreaming of nature-based solutions as drivers for a nature-based economy across the city, which is still less well embedded in city policy and strategy.
- A shift in the structure of Working Groups within the city from project-based to thematic-based (e.g. Water Management) has enabled a more strategic and integrated approach to project deliver. The new structure also has more influence due to Working Group members typically being more senior within organisation and strategic levels.
- In addition, through the 2020 Policy Cycle, sustainability is now embedded as one of three horizontal topics with Climate Action Planning and Nature-based Solutions now mainstreamed on delivery agendas of colleagues across the city authority. This includes transfer of the nature-based solution concept to a new flagship project climate-proofing the city centre through greening.
- Another example of changing governance within the City of Genk comprised a recognition of the need to increase the capacity of the Stiemervallei delivery team within the City Authority. This recognition has been reflected in expanded recruitment in the nature-based solution delivery team to work both within and beyond the Stiemervallei programme.

Financing and business models:

- City financing innovation included a focus on pooling regular resources within the space sector (e.g. nature management, bicycle connections, roads and water-related investments).
- In addition to securing the financing for delivery of the four spatial transformation projects, the successful grant capture at a Flemish level for operationalisation of the SuDS & Soda sub-project helped raise awareness of the effectiveness of adopting a nature-based solution approach in funding proposals. Accessing funding at a regional level has, historically, been viewed as challenging for the City of Genk. Thus, this latest success has led to broad acknowledgement of the value of the nature-based solution approach in funding proposals and is now being mainstreamed across other design/development approaches.

Nature-based Enterprises:

- Connecting Stiemer nature with entrepreneurship was a goal of the project team. In part, this was achieved by using the Stiemer Deals as a catalyst for economic development and entrepreneurship. However, a key aspect to delivery on this ambition will not be realised until the Stiemer sub-projects are more fully realised, and the attractiveness of the valley can be used as both a stimulus and a foundation for business, including nature-based enterprises.

Co-production:

- A professional communication strategy and recognisable visual language were established to reach and involve stakeholders. This was based on a process of creating

visibility and pride, promoting engagement through education and co-creation, and then driving active participation.

- The community engagement and communication strategy for the Stiemervallei programme are underpinned by the Friends of the Stiemer programme and Stiemer Deals. The Stiemer Deals programme adopted an entirely novel social innovation approach for the city: a voluntary agreement between the City of Genk and other partners from across the city (other city services, citizens, organizations, companies) in relation to delivering mutually aligned ambitions associated with the Stiemervallei. Officially launched in 2020, this innovative policy instrument is now integral to creating ecological, economic and social value from the Stiemervallei programme, delivering such innovations as Stiemer ice cream and Stiemer beer.
- Co-production activities ranged from the traditional to the more creative, including bicycle tours, neighbourhood dialogues, Stiemer quizzes, and the engagement of a Junior Team of local school children as child ambassadors.
- Social Innovation approaches developed through the Stiemervallei programme have also been expanded to include the City's New Energy Project.

Impact Assessment:

- A suite of environmental, social, and economic indicators has been implemented to establish a baseline for monitoring impact from the Stiemervallei programme as it rolls out. This has included engaging with a social-science-based Stiemerlab project that is monitoring the water quality of the Stiemer waterway. This will be used as a baseline for assessing change and there are discussions about broadening this approach to include monitoring SuDS & Soda. In addition, a Social/Health and Wellbeing survey has been carried out in the Stiemervallei catchment which will be repeated regularly to capture a measure of social change.

Reflexive Monitoring:

- A Stiemer diary process was implemented for all members of the Stiemer team to journal day-to-day activities. Explored as a team in monthly reflection sessions, the journals formed the basis for understanding the barriers and charting the successes of the Stiemer programme delivery.
- Following the successful implementation of the reflexive monitoring process on the Stiemer governance process, reflexive monitoring has now been transferred to the development of other major programmes within the City Authority.

Potential impacts/benefits:

- Real changes to the Stiemervallei surroundings through regeneration of an underused and neglected natural capital asset.
- Stormwater management (adopting a Sustainable Drainage Systems approach) and green space management (including enhancing/ conserving urban biodiversity) that create an attractive and functional blue-green zone turning a neglected area into the jewel in the crown of Genk.
- Urban regeneration (focusing on an active travel route with links to enterprise zones) as a mechanism to drive Genk to become a great place to live and work that is connected to its local nature and landscape.

- Collaboration between the authorities responsible for water management towards truly integrated management of the water in the Stiemervallei.
- Experiments with SuDS as a catalyst for mainstreaming the approach in Genk and regionally.
- Participatory planning and governance through active participation from the local population feeding into the new landscape plan for the Stiemerbeek.
- Social justice and social cohesion through locals and tourists alike (re)discovering a previous neglected area and using the Stiemervallei as an active travel route to move around Genk, to enjoy nature, and socialise.

NBS benefits

- Developing climate change adaptation; improving risk management and resilience
- Flood peak reduction
- Increase infiltration / Water storage
- Increasing infiltration
- Reduce flood risk
- Reduce load to sewer system
- Reduce run-off
- Reducing temperature at meso or micro scale
- Greater ecological connectivity across urban regenerated sites
- Improve connectivity and functionality of green and blue infrastructures
- Increase achievements of biodiversity targets
- Increase Biodiversity
- Increase quality and quantity of green and blue infrastructures
- Increased cultural richness and biodiversity
- Changing image of the urban environment
- Creation of green jobs relating to construction & maintenance of NBS
- Improve water quality
- Increase accessibility to green open spaces
- Increase awareness of NBS solution & their effectiveness and co benefits
- Increase communities' sense of ownership
- Increase population & infrastructures protected by NBS
- Increase social interaction
- Increase stakeholder awareness & knowledge about NBS
- Increase well-being
- Increase willingness to invest in NBS
- Provision of health benefits
- Social inclusion
- Social learning about location & importance of NBS

Transferability of the result:

Innovations developed as part of the Genk nature-based solution mainstreaming process have relevance to cities globally. In particular, they have direct relevance to the plethora of small/medium sized cities across the EU. Recognising some of the advantages and challenges of public administration on this scale, the Stiemervallei exemplar, and its spin-off innovations, represent excellent templates for maximising the value of limited public authority resources through a community-focused, and engaged, co-creation approach to regenerating a neglected community and city asset.

Lessons learned:

Based on the Reflexive Monitoring Learning Experience Workshop outcomes (WP2 Task 2.2)

Technical Solutions:

- To build SuDS into the exemplar in Genk, it was necessary to take a step backwards and explore how to build engagement and capacity for SuDS more fundamentally in the region. This is being achieved through the nature-based solution SuDS engagement and demonstrator as part of the SuDS & Soda project.
- Bringing a co-creative approach into tendering procedures enables the combining of different departmental goals into the Technical design.
- Building relations to break through silo thinking and overcome system boundaries in external organisations can unlock more multifunctional NBS design and financing. Bringing cities authorities together to influence this can bring more pressure to this than individual administrations.
- Failed funding proposals can represent a step forward in implementation if they act as a catalyst for multidisciplinary design collaboration.
- Recognition for the value of an NBS team and an NBS project can equate to recognition for a nature-based solution approach more broadly, particularly in relation to how they engage with their colleagues.

Governance:

- City-wide Thematic Working Group meetings are valuable for facilitating discussions with responsible actors in relation to 'safe-guarding' the vision of the masterplan during project development. They can also create new working dynamics, creating direct collaborations with external partners that would previously have been managed by another City Authority department.
- Collaboration with existing partners on new NBS approaches can create new symbiotic relationships, and can simplify procurement processes if collaboration covers different phases of planning and delivery.
- By changing the way of working into a co-productive approach, a collaborative governance model is created that can bridge communication gaps. This can be particularly beneficial when seeking innovative solutions for tendering NBS.
- Having a narrative that relates to wider city and Sustainable Development Goal strategies helps embed NBS approaches into policy plans by, for example, convincing decision-makers of the project's significance and herewith creating new relations. This

increased support leads to a new discourse around the project's significance and the implementation and scaling of NBS.

- Budgeting processes can have unwritten rules and important power relations that are challenging to navigate. It can be beneficial to form alliances with senior decision-makers to help navigate this.
- Taking ownership for policy plan actions can be an effective mechanism for ensuring that NBS becomes embedded at a higher governance level.
- The Stiemer Deals are an effective mechanism for unlocking 'dormant' capacity but require a novel way of governing by the city team (e.g. with regards to the contact point and facilitating the network) and collaboration with the purchasing department.
- When trying to drive change in local entrepreneurship around NBS, actors to facilitate change, embedded locally, allows long-term relationships to develop.
- Replication of the governance model to other sectors can provide insights into generic elements of a governance model.
- Working with a tailored communication strategy enables connecting activities to communication in a very initiative way, improving project governance.

Financing and business models:

- There is a need to embed NBS into the City's economics department. To do this, there is a need for capacity in terms of nature-based economy expertise and knowledge.
- New policy plans bring new financing challenges, but they can help to open up new funding opportunities.
- Collaborations developed during even failed funding proposals can create opportunities for new funding sources.
- Building a strong narrative to embed an NBS programme into city policy plans can represent a pathway for securing financing.
- Preparing a clear budget with detailed plans can make it easier for influential advocates to back a proposal for city funding.
- Embedding NBS programmes in policy plans can secure city budget as match funding for external funds.
- When working on tenders/applications that ask for complex solutions, fitting proposals into the system of the tender/application can represent a barrier.
- Citizen-orientated NBS public-private partnerships, can represent an effective financing approach.

Nature-based enterprises:

- Stimulation of entrepreneurship opportunities is an effective driver for securing NBS financing as part of regeneration processes.
- Nature-based enterprise creation, incubation, and acceleration is a unique challenge requiring sector specific understanding. This can be challenging for a city NBS team without such expertise.

Co-production:

- Including co-production processes with other departments into the preparation of tendering processes can help overcome gaps between vision and implementation.

- Co-production activities with external strategic actors can be an effective way of increasing delivery capacity by up-skilling partners to deliver their own projects independently.
- Knowledge collected in co-production processes can increase knowledge and capacity of community groups.
- ‘Clean-up’ campaigns can represent a gateway for wider engagement.
- Mapping and contacting local stakeholders based on spatial location, combined with mapping the social fabric of the area, can build a sense of belonging through the campaign.
- External organisations can help to build bridges between communities and the city team.
- Stiemer Deals proved to be a very effective co-production innovation for engaging actors and raising awareness.
- Co-producing a purchasing strategy with volunteers from NGOs can represent a barrier if volunteers are reluctant to take responsibility, particularly if there is a lack of clarity in relation to their role.
- Being locally embedded is important in relation to co-producing entrepreneurship due to the importance of the role of place.
- Building relationships with partners and citizens via informal, ‘fun’ activities strengthens more instrumental co-production initiatives.
- Including citizens (Friends of the Stiemer) in soundboard meetings with experts increases the awareness of experts for the impact on citizens and increases the commitment of the Friends of the Stiemer.

Impact assessment:

- Implementing a new policy plan also creates a need for new indicators to monitor its process.
- Implementing indicators does not need to mean entirely new processes and resources. It can be possible to utilise and/or supplement existing data generation processes.

Reflexive monitoring:

- The reflexive monitoring process has been one of the main success factors for the Genk Stiemer exemplar. A lot of effort was put into integrating the learning process into the overall governance and implementation strategy of the exemplar. A key insight has been the realisation that reflexive monitoring is a process that runs parallel to the regular project management, but at the same time is sufficiently interlinked.
- Many of the learning outcomes of the learning process have a relevance that exceeds the Stiemer programme. Many barriers sit at an organisational level of the municipality. The Stiemer programme offers great opportunities for organisational learning.
- The learning process ensures that the right things are done while the project management ensures that the things are done right. With the Stiemer programme, it is one of the first times for our urban transformation processes that we have succeeded to bridge the essential but very often missing link between the strategic ambitions of the City of Genk and the plethora of actions that are undertaken.

Financing:

Strategic project financing:

80% funding secured:

SuDS & Soda

- Public domain delivery funded through the transition of traditional Flanders Environment Agency funding mechanisms for grey infrastructure to also fund nature-based solutions experiments.
- Private domain and Living Lab co-financed by the regional Department of Environment and City of Genk.

Gardens of Waterschei

- 2.01 m€ investment funding from Regional Urban Policy Department, which is not only funding but mainly (and finally) recognition for the Stiemer Programme and the potential of nature-based solutions in city development.

Slagmolen

- Financing secured – city budgets itself + partly regional funds - Flemish Land Agency and Flanders Environment Agency.

Vallei Route

- Budget for first implementation of major missing link secured: city budget (+800.000 € extra in 2021) + regional cycling fund.

Legacy financing:

- Increased internal financing of the roles related to nature-based solution approaches to climate adaptation in the city authority. The responsible department will be extended with both strategic and operational profiles.
- A new proposal for Blue/Green Infrastructure for Regional Authorities is being written by the Connecting Nature team, using the Framework Elements and knowledge generated in Connecting Nature.
- Private sector finance is still a barrier.
- Innofins– research project on innovative financing of nature-based solutions at a Flemish level in partnership with the University of Antwerp.
- Exploring possibilities for further financing spatial transformation/Stiemerdeals through EU Life programme, supported by a Funding Officer contracted by the city for assistance in attracting EU funding.

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Deliverable 11 – Annex 2

Glasgow Nature-based Solution exemplar Case Study

DOCUMENT PROPERTIES

Nature Document	Deliverable 11 – Annex 2: Glasgow Nature-based Solution exemplar Case Study
Work Package	WP3
Task Leader	UEL
Authors	Lead author: Stuart Connop Contributors: Caroline Nash, Pauline Georgiou, Paula Vandergert, Petrut Madalin Gherase, Gillian Dick, Sean Kelly, Rania Sermpezi, Marleen Lodder, Katharina Hölscher, Carien van der Have, Siobhan McQuaid
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1		

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Open Space Strategy, Glasgow

Figure 1. Glasgow's Open Space Strategy showcasing how nature-based solutions can be interwoven into the city's urban fabric

Area characterisation:

Situated on the River Clyde in Scotland's West Central Lowlands, Glasgow is one of the UK's largest cities with over 600,000 inhabitants. The expansion of Glasgow's population was the result of a history of industrialisation which, at its peak, attracted a population of greater than one million residents. The rapid rate of urbanisation in Glasgow's past led to a range of social, environmental, and public health issues which the city attempted to address by delivering a range of municipal services and facilities. These included a public water supply and the construction of public parks on an unprecedented scale. The legacy of these public parks still serves large parts of the city well.

Following its population peak, a substantial decline in the city's industrial heart, meant that Glasgow had to transition to a new post-industrial future. With this transition came a variety of challenges at the heart of the city's DNA. This included:

- a large portion of the city's inhabitants being represented on the *Scottish index of multiple deprivation*.
- the *Glasgow Effect*, related to a significantly lower life expectancy in Glasgow than other urban areas in the UK and EU.

- Geographically-irregular changes in population, meaning that some open spaces became less frequently used and less valued.
- A post-industrial landscape that left a network of derelict contaminated and underused spaces.

Since the beginning of the 21st Century, the city's population has started to rise again and is expected to grow to 640,000 by 2039. This expansion is focused largely around tertiary sector industries such as financial and business services, communications, biosciences, creative industries, healthcare, higher education, retail and tourism. With this increase in population comes new demands on the city's open spaces. These include the use of open space for:

- dealing with surface water flooding, especially during and immediately after heavy rainfall events.
- providing habitats for nature, helping to enhance biodiversity.
- providing opportunities for delivering better, more coherent, and connected walking and cycling networks.
- providing convenient opportunities for outdoor recreation, sport, food growing, and general relaxation.
- mitigating poor air quality.
- contributing to a sense of place and a more attractive urban environment.

Nature-based solutions represent a viable solution for dealing with all of these demands on open space.

Figure 2. Glasgow Open Space Quantity Standard showing a measure of the quantity of accessible open space across the wards in Glasgow.

Slideshow:

Figure 3. Dawsholm Park open space. © Glasgow City Council.

Figure 4. Nature-based Academy participants visiting Toryglen Woods. © Glasgow City Council.

Figure 5. Nature-based Academy Participants visiting Urban Roots Community Garden. © Glasgow City Council.

Figure 6. Growchapel Garden - Community Area. © Glasgow City Council.

Figure 7. Growchapel Garden Therapy plaque. © Glasgow City Council.

Figure 8. Growchapel rainy but packed opening day. © Glasgow City Council.

Objectives:

Meeting these multifaceted demands on Glasgow's open spaces is going to be important in ensuring that Glasgow is well-equipped to deal with the challenges of the 21st century and to enhance the attractiveness of the city as a place in which to live and invest.

As part of the Connecting Nature project, the City of Glasgow's ambition was to develop, and begin to deliver, an Open Space Strategy for the city to help address this changing context and the changing demands on open space. The aim was for the Strategy to be used to establish an approach for considering the different ways in which the people, flora and fauna of Glasgow will need to make use of open space, now and in the future. By adopting a nature-based solution approach to this challenge, the ambition was to not only understand these competing demands, but to also consider them in relation to how open spaces are funded, managed, and created to deliver multifunctional environmental, social, and economic benefits. Such an approach was intended to underpin decision-making in relation to how open spaces are resourced during a challenging financial climate that is delivering fewer resources to create new open spaces, or to enhance and maintain existing ones.

The Open Space Strategy was developed to set out an overarching approach to the city's open spaces, providing strategic direction that would guide the work, policy-making, and investment decisions of all Glasgow Council services and other members of the Council family, to deliver an effective and fully-functioning green network of open spaces and other green/blue infrastructure interventions. Once developed, this network would help to make Glasgow more resilient in the face of challenges such as climate change, more liveable, and more effective at unlocking the value of its natural capital. Ultimately, helping the City of Glasgow to continue to flourish.

Specific sub-objectives in relation to these overarching ambitions include:

- Ensuring that greenspace is valued in terms of its function within the larger green-blue system, including increasing awareness amongst local community of the contribution these spaces can make in relation to large urban-generated environmental problems.
- Increased local stakeholder-led engagement and entrepreneurship in relation to open spaces.
- Green networks delivering greater positive outcomes such as jobs, safety, physical and mental health.
- Greater financial investment in green/blue water management solutions and greater recognition of the value of urban water as a resource.
- Unlocking of previously contaminated and inaccessible areas.
- Broader mechanisms to activate 'stalled spaces' and to drive scaled-up urban agriculture.
- Positive secondary impacts (co-benefits) such as safer streets and public spaces, physical and mental health has been improved.
- A collective sense of the value of Glasgow, at a city scale, as a connected city.

Actions:

- Development of the Open Space Strategy, and follow up activities that are securing its rollout across the city, have been delivered through diverse transformational activities aligned with the elements of the [Connecting Nature NBS Framework: Governance; Financing and business models; Nature-based enterprises; Co-production; Impact Assessment; and Reflexive Monitoring](#).

Technical Solutions:

- The [Open Space Strategy](#) nature-based solutions exemplar has been developed, peer-reviewed, and adopted by the council. It is now shaping urban planning and development activities across the city.
- An Open Space Quality Assessment was developed and carried out on all amenity greenspace, parks and public gardens and other open space types that can have multiple uses and are >0.3 ha across the city. This provided a foundation for understanding both the current state of open spaces and the future potential.
- A Connecting Nature spatial database was developed to map the social, economic, and environmental context across Glasgow. The Open Space Quality Assessment was included in the database which is now being used as a tool for understanding the local context needs when planning optimal nature-based solutions design, delivery, and stewardship. The tool is being used across departments/themes including the Development Plan, playspace revitalisation, urban agriculture, water management, and the Woodland Strategy.
- Building from the spatial database development, Glasgow City Council (GCC) is partnering with NatureScot, the Scottish Government, and Dark Matters Labs to develop TreesAI: an open-source platform to map, value and finance urban forests. This will underpin better decision-making in relation to tree planting, management, and stewardship. The project was piloted at COP26 and will subsequently represent a funding stream for mainstreaming nature-based solutions across the city.
- The Open Space Strategy is also being rolled out incrementally through individual projects. For example, the [Growchapel community garden](#) – a co-created community allotment facility recently launched in the city to promote social interaction within the community, healthy eating, outdoor activity and other health and wellbeing impacts.

Governance:

- Innovation actions in relation to governance focused on developing an interdepartmental approach for the Open Space Strategy to provide a framework for collaboration and co-financing across the city council and externally.
- The Open Space Strategy has contributed to the restructuring of the Sustainability and Planning departments to align them with the Development Plan group. Also, with the declaration of a Climate Emergency and Ecological Emergency by the council.
- A Climate Plan was developed alongside the Corporate Climate Liaison Group. Both of which were co-led by the Glasgow Connecting Nature team lead.
- An additional governance action was the production of an Elected Members Briefing on nature-based solutions, developed jointly with COSLA, The Improvement Service, and Nature Scot.

- The Scottish UrbanByNature Hub also represents a governance action in development. The Hub will drive knowledge exchange and build capacity in relation to nature-based solution implementation. The Glasgow Connecting Nature team engaged several stakeholder organisations including statutory nature, environment, and planning organisations, and local authority network representatives, to co-create this strategic knowledge exchange platform.
- The Connecting Nature Framework was used as a tool to review and then relaunch the strategic Stalled Spaces programme that has been running in Glasgow for the last 10 years. It identified the need to provide more support to communities around the key areas identified within the framework, and that project identification, mapping, and signposting were critical. This opened discussions with Community Land Scotland around community ownership, and the Scottish Land Commission. It was also used to leverage £150k of Vacant and Derelict Land funding in Drumchapel.

Financing and business models:

- A key focus of the Corporate Climate Liaison Group was exploring the finances necessary to deliver the Climate Plan. Resources are coming through the Climate Plan to the Sustainability team that will be used to deliver on the OSS.
- Work is ongoing to secure resources for roles extending beyond the duration of the Connecting Nature project for delivering the Open Space Strategy and nature-based solutions.
- As proof of concept for the Open Space Strategy approach, £500K has been secured from the Scottish Government through Parks & Operation Department to deliver and update playspaces across the city. The project will be developed as a pilot for the Open Space Strategy approach, with the intention that this will be mainstreamed for the subsequent £5m that the Scottish Government will be investing in open space improvements. The Parks & Operation department are collaborating with the Connecting Nature team by using the NBS spatial dataset to better understand locations with the potential to deliver the greatest benefits to local communities, and the co-benefits that can be delivered through nature-based solution approaches.
- Trees AI represents a public-private funded collaboration to develop a tool for scaling private sector investment in urban nature-based solutions in Glasgow. The tool uses an intelligent system of understanding and valuing carbon credits and ecosystem service provision to unlock delivery and stewardship funding.

Nature-based Enterprises:

- The initiating action for nature-based enterprises was to map the current innovation ecosystem and to consider where innovation in nature-based entrepreneurship/enterprise (NBE) might fit.
- Following this, Glasgow City Council partnered The Melting Pot's Good Ideas and Glasgow Caledonian University in establishing an NBE accelerator pilot programme to support early-stage nature-based businesses. With 40 quality applications for the initial 10 places, the programme was heavily oversubscribed. Due to this demand, enrolment was increased to 15 high potential start-ups, all of which undertook the

accelerator programme, graduating in September 2021. Following this success, there are now plans to develop this programme further.

Co-production:

- Co-production was delivered at two levels. Firstly, at strategic level in relation to the Open Space Strategy. For this, co-production was used as a method to engage with various stakeholders at multiple levels of the process of developing and implementing the Open Space Strategy.
- Open Space Strategy co-production included public consultation using a blend of innovative approaches for the council including online questionnaires, public exhibitions, and key questions on postcards distributed through the city's Library and Council Office network.
- Secondly, co-production was focused on a nature-based solution strategic pilot project level, demonstrating the rollout potential of the Open Space Strategy. This included co-production workshops as part of the development of Growchapel (including applying the Nature-Based Solutions Business Model Canvas method), the redevelopment of the Burrell Museum in Pollok Park, and the next iteration of the city's Stalled Spaces programme to include a greater focus on nature-based solutions.
- Co-production approaches were also used for the development of the new Food Growing Strategy. The Nature-Based Solutions Business Model Canvas was used as the catalyst for this, creating a narrative around which potential social, environmental, health and economic benefits could be better articulated and realised.
- Co-production approaches have led to the co-development of *Every Tree Tells a Story*: a social cohesion and lived experience NBS project to capture and map tree stories across the city. Co-designed with Strathclyde University and GCC Education Improvement Service, it seeks to empower communities to use creativity to capture stories about the trees and the spaces in which they sit.
- The co-production skills developed by the Connecting Nature team have also allowed them to support and partner in the Hidden Environmental Histories of the Clyde project.

Impact Assessment:

- The Glasgow Connecting Nature team have worked to develop a suite of indicators to evaluate the impact of nature-based solutions at both a city level (to monitor the incremental impact of the open space strategy) and at a local level (to monitor the impact of individual nature-based solution pilots). Research was undertaken in the summer of 2019, to identify potential data sources for the indicators and to build a baseline for the City of Glasgow. This led to new interdepartmental collaborations across Glasgow City Council and external collaboration with partners including the National Health Service Greater Glasgow and Clyde, the Biological Record Centre, Glasgow Caledonian University, and the Scottish Government. For some indicators, it was not possible to identify a partner able to supply the data. For these, it was necessary to implement new evaluation processes, some of which are expected to be picked up following the end of this Horizon 2020 project.

- In parallel to the indicator development, a dashboard was created to as a way to map and represent some of the existing baseline of health, social, environmental and economic trends across the city. The aim being to provide a baseline for comparison of the future outcomes of the city’s Open Space Strategy and the impacts of nature-based solution implementation across the city. The dashboard allows viewers to visualize the interplay of different indicators (e.g. health status, social deprivation, greenspace distribution) in a particular city location. As such, it is a useful instrument for identifying types of indicators and data that might be missing, thus orienting future impact assessment decisions. It is also valuable in terms of informing strategic planning of nature-based solution design and management, in order to meet local needs.
- The development of the suite of indicators has supported knowledge sharing with the local universities and has allowed co-production of a NERC bid called Gallant.
- Connecting Nature brought in a GIS officer to support this evaluation impact indicator and dashboard development. Work is ongoing to secure the legacy of this GIS position, to ensure continuity of the spatial analysis and impact evaluation components of the Open Space Strategy through the Glasgow City Dashboard.
- Working with Connecting Nature partners, Glasgow City Council also co-developed an interactive evaluation impact planning tool (Co-Impact). A prototype of the tool has been developed and tested, and a version for launch is underdevelopment. The tool supports users in identifying appropriate indicators for impact evaluation and provides links to appropriate metrics for implementing these.
- Development has begun on a Scottish UrbanByNature Hub. This will include a focus on impact assessment to align with the Scottish Government priorities in relation to Digital Planning and Data.

Figure 9. Glasgow City Council spatial data dashboard

Reflexive Monitoring:

- Reflexive Monitoring methodologies were adopted and adapted by the Glasgow Connecting Nature team to support the development and implementation of the Open Space Strategy.
- Key learning outcomes from the Reflexive Monitoring process included recognition of the value of developing a business model canvas to improve communication to colleagues in relation to exploring and communicating the nature-based solution exemplar aims.
- Reflexive Monitoring also raised awareness of the barriers related to Glasgow City Council procurement and recruitment practices when developing nature-based solutions.
- Reflexive Monitoring methods were adapted by the Glasgow Connecting Nature team in order to simplify the process. This further encouraged the participation of key colleagues in different services and helped to reduce silo-working practices.

Potential impacts/benefits:

At their most basic level, the key impacts from the Glasgow City Council Open Space Strategy nature-based solution exemplar will be:

- A raised awareness across the city of the value of a nature-based solutions approach to the planning, delivery, and stewardship of the city's Open Spaces.
- Silo-busting through a shared recognition of common goals and opportunities across the City Council's departments, and a pathway for collaboration with external stakeholders across the city through a shared vision.
- More integrated planning decision-making linked to spatially explicit and accessible data on needs, pressures, and opportunities.
- More integrated financing through the delivery of shared goals and opportunities.
- Creation of a stronger link between Glasgow's Open Spaces and the needs of the communities using them.
- Adoption of nature-based solution approaches to other grey/green/blue infrastructure components across the city.

NBS benefits

Due to the nature of the Open Space Strategy and the almost universal potential to shape nature-based solution delivery across the city. The potential benefits will be far reaching. These will include:

- Developing climate change adaptation, improving risk management and resilience:
 - Flood peak reduction
 - Increase infiltration/Water storage
 - Reduce flood risk
 - Reduce load to sewer system
 - Reduce run-off
 - Reducing temperature at meso or micro scale

- Developing climate change mitigation:
 - Carbon sequestration and storage
 - More energy efficient buildings
- Restoring ecosystems and their functions:
 - Greater ecological connectivity across urban regenerated sites
 - Improve connectivity and functionality of green and blue infrastructures
 - Increase achievements of biodiversity targets
 - Increase biodiversity
 - Increase quality and quantity of green and blue infrastructures
 - Increased cultural richness and biodiversity
- Enhancing sustainable urbanisation:
 - Changing image of the urban environment
 - Creation of green jobs relating to construction & maintenance of NBS
 - Improve air quality
 - Improve water quality
 - Increase accessibility to green open spaces
 - Increase amount of green open spaces for residents
 - Increase awareness of NBS solution & their effectiveness and co benefits
 - Increase communities' sense of ownership
 - Increase population & infrastructures protected by NBS
 - Increase social interaction
 - Increase stakeholder awareness & knowledge about NBS
 - Increase well-being
 - Increase willingness to invest in NBS
 - Provision of health benefits
 - Reduce costs for water treatments
 - Social inclusion
 - Social learning about location & importance of NBS

Transferability of the results:

Innovations developed as part of the Glasgow Open Space Strategy NBS mainstreaming process have relevance to cities globally. In particular, they have direct relevance to large cities struggling with the challenges of siloed working across disparate teams and operating with diminishing and isolated funding streams. By using nature-based solutions to promote shared delivery on strategic priorities and underpinning this with an evidence-base to inform decision-making and to promote interdisciplinary planning across the public administration, the Glasgow Open Space Strategy represents an excellent template for maximising the value of public authority resources.

Glasgow is creating a place-based approach, with a nature-based lens, to work with their citizens to make the city more climate adaptive. This approach is transferrable to cities globally.

Lessons learned:

Based on the Reflexive Monitoring Learning Experience Workshop outcomes (WP2 Task 2.2)

Technical Solutions:

- Site visits are a very effective mechanism for evaluating the topography, constraints, access, etc, when planning nature-based solutions. However, they also have a greater value: site visits can be an effective mechanism for strengthening relationships with, and learning about projects from, colleagues from other departments. Such face-to-face conversations provide opportunity for more informal conversations that can strengthen collaboration between colleagues from different departments.
- Strategically, using high-level initiatives such as COP26 and the Climate Emergency announcements can be an effective way to increase awareness around the multifunctional benefits of nature-based solutions.
- Technical demonstrators are also an effective way to raise the profile of nature-based solutions by demonstrating what can be achieved in a local context.
- Another effective mechanism for engaging others in Technical Solution delivery was aligning with the National Park City campaign. The campaign involved a network of delivery actors who represented key contacts for nature-based solution delivery.

Governance:

- There was a lack of consistent, established, and agreed internal cross-service governance structure at management/senior management level. A novel Open Space team meeting was established to address this. The meeting comprised key officers at operational management level focused across the 15 themes of the Open Space Strategy. The meeting formalised what was previously an informal networking process.
- Collaboration for the NBE accelerator programme represented governance innovation for the City Council Connecting Nature team as it partnered with the Centre for Civic Innovation and utilised their networks.
- A shift towards co-productive model working with ‘Friends of’ groups represented a governance shift in relation to delivery. Out-sourcing delivery and providing support in the form of capacity building resources, represented a new way of working.
- Delivery of the Open Space Strategy also required new ways of governing how the council managed their assets across departments. Property Sales, in particular, required the creation of new relations (less formal, better working relationships) between the departments at strategic levels and new practices for collaboration.
- Story mapping methodology was used to showcase funding opportunities, to share learning, and as an engagement tool. Visually representing nature-based solution concepts helped underpin discussions with other policy makers.
- The focus on using the Open Space Strategy to inform the development of outdoor play and learning spaces also represented governance innovation for the city, due to the cross-departmental collaboration and support processes.

Financing and business models:

- The Open Space Strategy provides a mechanism for combining departmental budgets under the new governance structure. This facilitates easier access to multiple budgets and better value for money across budgets.
- Capacity-building of community groups also included a focus on financing to support out-scaling of nature-based solutions delivery beyond the Glasgow Connecting Nature team. This focused on unlocking different kinds of funding that would not be accessible to the council.
- Participation as hosts of COP26 has brought much focus on Glasgow and has presented broader opportunities in relation to pilot/proof-of-concept financing. Similarly, participation in the National Park City campaign has opened additional new funding opportunities.
- Story mapping was an effective mechanism for showcasing funding opportunities.

Nature-based enterprises:

- The Open Space Strategy provided an effective framework for generating a nature-based economy around nature-based solutions planning, delivery, and stewardship.
- The Nature-Based Enterprise accelerator programme was an effective mechanism for knowledge transfer to nature-based enterprises in relation to how enterprises could source funding and what sort of business modelling they could adopt.
- The Nature-Based Enterprise accelerator programme partners have recently been awarded research resource from a Glasgow School of Art research team to carry out a systems-led review of the pilot. The aim of this is to assess the progress of the Nature-Based Academy participants as well as help to begin to forge a local Nature-Based Enterprise ecosystem in Glasgow.
- COP26 networks provided connections to multiple nature-based enterprises.
- A novel collaboration with the nature-based enterprise - Urban Good - expanded the Open Space Strategy to more layers, e.g. showing uses of open space. Urban Good also produced offline paper maps, making them accessible to different audiences.

Co-production:

- A co-production approach was effective for producing the teaching programme for the Nature-Based Enterprise accelerator. This was done through collaboration with the Glasgow Connecting Nature team and local partners.
- Learning from the way communities organised themselves during COVID around local challenges provided important lessons in terms of the need for Nature-Based Solutions in specific areas.
- The pandemic did not mean an end to co-production with 'Friends of' groups. Instead, it represented a new way of establishing these community groups. Virtual and hybrid approaches were effective, and sometimes meant greater engagement. It also led to the creation of videos for supporting capacity building which were a more sustainable legacy compared to one-off workshops.
- Co-production processes can provide a valuable source of knowledge/data when mapping local environmental, social, and economic context.

- Steering committee approaches to pilot project delivery with community representatives on the committees was an effective foundation for facilitating co-production processes with local stakeholders.

Impact assessment:

- If carried out at a city scale, the value of impact assessment extends beyond just evidencing the impact of a nature-based solution pilot. By bringing disparate datasets together into a central resource it is possible to also support more integrated and targeted decision-making for nature-based solution planning by promoting data sharing and interdepartmental working.
- In addition to city-scale indicators, local scale evaluation of pilots can be used to raise the profile of central strategy, enhancing the ability to continue nature-based solution delivery beyond the Horizon 2020 project funding.
- Moving from informal evaluation to formal evaluation helps to mainstream nature-based solution implementation from one driven by anecdotal evidence to a robust science-based approach based on hard data.

Reflexive monitoring:

- The structure of the Open Space meeting was inspired by the Reflexive Monitoring process, the learnings sessions, how the team internally discussed the tracker, and how they prepared for the reflexive monitoring meetings.
- The Glasgow team discovered that it was best to simplify the Reflexive Monitoring process when carrying out these meetings. They identified a team member to undertake each Reflexive Monitoring role and to undertake the tracker updates and structured notes post-meeting, to avoid complicating the process for colleagues who only engaged with matters on an ad-hoc basis. The Connecting Nature team also found it valuable to discuss how the process worked with other colleagues who expressed an interest in adopting Reflexive Monitoring as a method for use in other projects.

Financing:

Strategic project financing:

- Financing has been focused at two strategic levels. The first level was targeting strategic funding for city-wide rollout of the Open Space Strategy. The second level was the establishment of strategic pilot projects to showcase what can be achieved using a Nature-Based Solution approach to Open Spaces.
- At a city-wide level:
 - £500K was secured from the Scottish Government through Parks & Operation Department to deliver and update playspaces across the city. The project represents a steppingstone to accessing a future Scottish Government fund of £5m for Open Space improvements.
 - The Trees AI project represents a public-private funded collaboration which secured support from The Google.org Impact Challenge on Climate: a £10m

fund supporting 12 challenges across Europe. In Glasgow, the collaboration will develop a tool for scaling private sector investment in urban nature-based solutions in Glasgow.

- Pilot project funding included:
 - £3k seed funding to kick-start the Bellahouston Demonstration Garden opened in 2017;
 - £70k funding for the Growchapel Community Garden from a range of sources;
 - A combination of Glasgow City Council (£35k), Glasgow Housing Association (£15k), and an additional £10-15k from external parties to fund the revised Stalled Spaces programme with a greater focus on sustainable nature-based solutions projects. This revised programme included funding engagement of an NGO (The Conservation Volunteers) to increase the capacity of

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Deliverable 11 – Annex 3

Poznań Nature-based Solution exemplar Case Study

DOCUMENT PROPERTIES

Nature Document	Deliverable 11 – Annex 3: Poznań Nature-based Solution exemplar Case Study
Work Package	WP3
Task Leader	UEL
Authors	Lead author: Stuart Connop Contributors: Caroline Nash, Pauline Georgiou, Paula Vandergert, Petrut Madalin Gherase, Agnieszka Osipiuk, Agnieszka Dziubala, Natalia Madajczyk, Dominika Dymek, Marleen Lodder, Katharina Hölscher, Carien van der Have, Siobhan McQuaid
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Network of small-scale nature-based solutions in Poznań

Figure 1. Eco-garden installed at one of Poznań's kindergartens as part of the Connecting Nature exemplar.

Area characterisation:

Poznan lies on the Warta River in west-central Poland, in the Greater Poland region. With a population of 533,000, it is the fifth largest city by population in Poland. In terms of footprint, however, it is a relatively compact city. Poznan is an important academic site, with about 130,000 students and the third largest Polish university. The city has often topped rankings for very high quality of education and a very high standard of living. It also ranks highly in safety and healthcare quality.

Poznań is a city rich in green spaces. The morphology of the city is still marked by a system of green rings and green wedges proposed by the urbanist Władysław Czarnecki in the 1930s. The green wedges roughly follow the existing natural geographical structure of the city where smaller rivers (the Bogdanka, Cybina and Główna as well as the Głuszynka and Michałowka) meet up with the Warta River streaming from south to north. Today, the majority of the green wedges are covered with forests which under current zoning plans cannot be used for construction. On the suburbs of the city, the green ring-wedge system has a forest character and connects with regional forests in a larger scale. Inside the city boundaries, there are also around 8,500 hectares of agricultural land that has less strict protection in planning, especially if left fallow after the collapse of collective agriculture in the early 1990s. The green wedges provide value and function for the city of Poznan.

The system has come under a lot of pressure during recent years from development with a rapidly expanding retail market that creates demand for housing development. In addition to the housing, associated population increase, and the need for new infrastructure, creates additional pressures in relation to the need for stormwater management, and the pressure for additional parking spaces. The green wedge design also means that greenspace is not equally distributed in the city. Despite the green wedges penetrating deep into the city, dense built-up districts in the historical areas lack greenspace and key challenges that the city faces, like noise and pollution (associated with traffic), rainwater management (sewage overflow and flooding), and temperature swings (from Urban Heat Island Challenges in summer to extreme cold in winter) are exacerbated.

Figure 2. Areas of greenery and recreation across the City of Poznań, showing the green wedge system.

Slideshow:

Figure 3. Natural playgrounds and eco-demonstrators in Poznań's preschools (© Miasto Poznan)

Figure 4. Floating garden on Cybina River in Poznań. © Michał Strokowski

Objective:

The challenge for Poznań is to improve the quality of life in those areas that do not have equitable access to greenspace due to being very urbanised and with higher population densities. By focusing on nature-based solution approaches to deliver this, it is possible to reverse the city's trend towards a rate of high soil sealing in the city centre's densely built-up residential areas, which exacerbate climate change impacts, particularly during heat waves and episodic flooding from intense rainfall.

The City of Poznan Connecting Nature team identified pocket parks and urban gardens as a mechanism to deliver these objectives. The Poznań nature-based solution exemplar aims to implement small-scale nature-based solution interventions across the city with a particular focus on those areas that are densely urbanised and inhabited by citizens who currently have limited access to greenery. Such an 'out-scaling' approach relies on replicated small interventions, rather than requiring substantial individual areas of land. Out-scaling also enables the extension of the network of green infrastructure in Poznań, complementing the green wedges which run through the city, from north to south and from east to west. Creating these nature spaces will increase the stepping-stone connectivity between existing key green infrastructure assets to facilitate the movement of biodiversity, in addition to people, across the city.

The initial focus of this out-scaling was on the delivery of a series of eco- and social-gardens at kindergartens across the city. Kindergartens were identified as a key objective as these represented a pre-existing network across the city at which nature-based solutions would deliver accessibility and climate change adaptation targets. Also providing play and educational benefits to local kindergarten children. Poznań's nature-based solution exemplar represents a unique challenge given the large scale of the city, and the balance the city needs to strike between the multiple demands on its open spaces. In this respect, nature-based solutions represent functional solutions that can be integrated into the existing urban structure and functions of the city.

Creating attractive nature-based solutions in the city centre (close to the historical centre of the city) is also expected to increase tourist attractiveness. Regenerating other centrally located green spaces (e.g. the Warta river valley) have shown to increase the flow of people in these areas and prompts an interest in neighbouring areas that result in a collaborative desire to regenerate old, abandoned, or neglected spaces. This is a vital factor in place-making. These improvements can also attract new inhabitants. Improved districts are now becoming fashionable and many new business endeavours of local collaboration are emerging.

Actions:

- The nature-based solutions exemplar programme is coordinated by the Project Coordination and Urban Regeneration Office of Poznań City Hall.
- Delivery of the NBS exemplar ecogardens (eco-demonstrators), natural playgrounds, as well as floating gardens has been initiated through a diversity of transformational

activities aligned with the elements of the [Connecting Nature NBS Framework](#): [Technical Solutions](#); [Governance](#); [Financing and business models](#); [Nature-based enterprises](#); [Co-production](#); [Impact Assessment](#); and [Reflexive Monitoring](#).

Technical Solutions:

- Technical Solutions delivery has focused on the multifunctional design of the NBS exemplars to balance trade-offs in relation to delivering local benefits (based on the immediate needs of the users and locality) and broader benefits (based on key strategic needs of the city). This has included a design focus on the creation of aesthetics balanced with functional spaces that attract a high degree of activity, daily interactions, and social gatherings. A series of different nature-based solution spatial transformation projects have been delivered across the city:
- Current status of spatial transformation projects –
 - *Eco-demonstrators* – are elements made of natural materials (plants, wood, etc) representing ecological and environmental phenomena. For example: insect houses, garden wooden pots/flower beds filled with compost soil for planting, live willow huts, numerous climbers (plants) or fruit bushes. Education class scenarios were also prepared, to be used by teachers in conducting ecological education classes with the use of eco-demonstrators installed in preschool gardens. These nature-based solutions have been successfully out-scaled since the start of Connecting Nature. Overall, at least 10 pre-schools have received eco-demonstrators in their playspaces each year since 2018. In total, there are now 46 pre-schools with eco-demonstrators.
 - *Natural playgrounds* - the nature oriented-playgrounds are unique places created for pre-school children where, alongside the play equipment, there are elements of nature. This includes sandy hills, live willow huts, and paths made from logs and stumps. These are supplemented with green flowerbeds, fruit bushes, and houses that allow children to grow their own plants or observe insects. These "play gardens" are more than just a playground, giving children and their guardians the opportunity to experience nature directly, and creating additional accessible greenspace in the city. As part of the Connecting Nature project, three nature-oriented playgrounds were created in gardens of nursery schools No. 42, No. 46 and No. 87 in 2017-2018. Since this initial success, a total of twenty-one nature-orientated playgrounds have now been installed in Poznań kindergartens.
 - *Floating gardens* - in partnership with the OnWater Foundation, five floating gardens have been completed in Poznań (two on Cybina River, three on ponds in parks in Poznań). The floating gardens improve the river/water ecosystem, introducing more biodiversity into the city by providing shelter, feeding, and breeding opportunities. The vegetation cover on them is predominantly native species, supporting local biodiversity targets, but with the potential for additional colonisation. The gardens also impact on water quality by providing a filtration/water purification function.
 - *Open gardens* – One of the pre-Connecting Nature actions: the Open Garden at Kindergarten No. 42 in Wilda was a pilot project implemented by the Project Coordination and Urban Regeneration Office in cooperation with Kindergarten No. 42 and the NGO's (Zieleniak Project) initiative. The aim of

the project was to develop a garden which would be opened for both the kindergarten children and also for residents of Wilda District in Poznań. The Open Garden is a combination of the idea of a social garden and a natural playground, open to children and adults, especially those using the kindergarten, the neighbouring nursery and primary school, as well as residents of nearby tenement houses. It is a place where children can experience nature, adults can rest, and people can get actively involved growing plants. The project was initiated in 2017 and the garden was finally opened in March 2018. In the period from April to June 2018, a series of weekend family workshops was held in the garden, engaging the residents and promoting the idea of the open garden. Due to necessity, the garden had to be closed to residents during the COVID19 pandemic. However, this provided space for the team to develop new ideas for open gardens at kindergartens in Poznań. There were some interesting collaborations but often, due to lack of finances, organizational barriers, and a pandemic, it was not possible to open new open gardens in the city. At the time of writing, there is only one open garden at preschool no. 42 in Poznań.

Governance:

- A focus of governance innovation for the exemplar has been on identifying, engaging, and facilitating the smooth cooperation and transfer of information between different departments and partners engaged in the process. Central to this was facilitating a collaborative approach between the Project Coordination and Urban Regeneration Office (design part in the frame of CN), the Department Of Education (managing budget earmarked for investments in kindergartens on the basis of multiannual programme created by Poznań City Council), and the individual kindergarten leads (responsible for applying to the Department of Education for the grant for investment, and choosing the way of designing and maintaining their investments).
- In order to ensure the engagement of senior decision and policy-makers, it was also critical to map the expected benefits of the Open and Social Gardens programme onto key city strategies (Development Strategy for the City of Poznań 2020+; Development Strategy of the Warta River in Poznań; Study of Conditions and Directions of Spatial Development of the City of Poznań Environmental Protection Program for the City of Poznań; Municipal Revitalization Program for the City of Poznań; Plan for Sustainable Development of Public Transport for the City of Poznań for 2014-2025; Plan of Adaptation to Climate Change for the city of Poznań to 2030) to demonstrate how the NBS exemplar would deliver on these.
- The “Open Garden” located in densely urbanised district of Wilda represented another governance challenge. In this case, exploring how the attractive greenspaces associated the many public institutions in the city could be expanded for use beyond the “usual users”. Governance innovation comprised a collaborative approach towards partial opening of such spaces to citizens who are usually restricted from coming to their premises. A balance of openness and flexibility from the public institution and respect for rules of conduct defined by the users was necessary, which was achieved using co-creation approaches.
- In parallel to the technical delivery of the natural playgrounds, a series of information activities promoting the idea of natural playgrounds were organised. This included a

seminar on "Natural playgrounds in pre-school gardens" at the Poznań International Fair as part of a two-day conference "Education for public space". The workshops included activities in which the directors and teachers of nursery schools tried their hand at designing their own kindergarten natural playgrounds, under the supervision of an expert. These events were designed to build awareness of, and demand for, nature-based approaches to playspaces at kindergartens and schools, both at an academic and political level.

- This approach has been supplemented with the production of a locally-contextualised catalogue of NBS to raise awareness of the approach in Poznań.

Financing and business models:

- Initial financing focused on innovation in relation to a hybrid model of financing nature-based solutions by combining different departmental budgets, with external kindergarten budgets, and with resources from the Connecting Nature project. In order to scale finances to include implementation at primary schools, additional EU external funding is being sought.
- To continue the scaling of nature-based solution approaches, it was necessary to expand financing. In order to open up new external funding opportunities, the Connecting Nature team uses their NBS catalogue to engage civil servants and developers.
- To exploit diverse funding opportunities, the Connecting Nature team are also exploring cooperative approaches with the private sector through sponsorship-based approach.

Entrepreneurship:

- The City of Poznań developed an Entrepreneurship Programme launched at the [Connecting Nature Enterprise Summit](#). The programme comprised of two parts:
 - Education for decision-makers.
 - Training on good practice for contractors/NBEs.
- In addition, technical training materials were produced that could be shared with city and district councillors responsible for making budget decisions on a district level. This is being supplemented with an additional training cycle in relation to animating and maintaining natural playspaces. This approach to engaging entrepreneurship with nature-based solutions is being expanded to include other types of NBS (e.g. Floating gardens or rain gardens).

Co-production:

- The process of co-production was not a commonly used method in project work prior to Connecting Nature, especially in public administration institutions, such as city halls. The innovative method had to be learnt. Many of the principles were already implicitly known, but they were not used on a daily basis and as operating practice.
- The introduction of open gardens at preschools and other public institutions plays a central role in the place-making process. As such, cooperation between different stakeholders is a key part of the design process for these green interventions. Novel co-production processes (based on the [Connecting Nature Guidebook](#) principles of

initiating, consultation, implementation and a continuous process) were trailed to support collaborative working between the Connecting Nature team, the Education Department, the Kindergarten managers, and the nature-based solution designers. For the ‘open gardens’ the local community user groups represented an additional stakeholder engaged in the co-production process.

- For the novel nature-based solution approach to conserving and broadening participation in the allotment gardens, the organisation ‘Go and Sow’ were contracted to spearhead this. Their actions included engaging a broader representation of the community in allotment use through a co-production approach. Allotments in the city centre are in competition from other types of greenspace which are more open to citizens. The co-production process has been used to explore how allotments can be opened up as more accessible greenspace, to ensure that they are protected as a key component of Poznań’s green infrastructure, removing any risk of redevelopment as grey infrastructure.

Impact Assessment:

- Poznań’s approach to navigating the challenges of evaluating impact was addressed through strong partnership working with Adam Mickiewicz University. Through this partnership, the Poznań Connecting Nature team were able to implement environmental, social, and economic indicators for capturing the multifunctional value of their nature-based solution exemplar:
 - *Environmental impact monitoring* focused on aspects including direct measurement of temperature and humidity combined with an index for evaluating biodiversity net-gain in the open garden, preschool gardens and pocket parks.
 - *Social indicators* represented a unique challenge due to COVID19 limiting the occupancy of the kindergartens, and therefore the use of the natural playspaces. However, some surveys were able to be conducted among teachers, directors and parents.
 - *Economic indicators* were focused on ‘value’ for money. This has included interviews with contractors and ecosystem service valuation.

Reflexive monitoring

- Reflexive monitoring represented a new method for the Poznań City Connecting Nature team. Prior to its implementation as a project management tool, problems and difficulties in different aspects of the city team’s work were analysed in team meetings, but no specific tools were used to monitor them.
- Reflexive Monitoring proved to be a useful process for supporting coordination of this complex, multifaceted project. It provided a mechanism for managing strategic sub-projects, analysing gaps, and identifying resources and activities to address them. It also provided a strategic overview of the situation within the lead organisation, reflecting the context of exemplar implementation and goal attainment through associated activities of other city units.

Potential impacts/benefits:

Planning, delivery, and stewardship of the nature-orientated playgrounds and open gardens generated a diversity of benefits. Firstly, those related directly to the impacts from the gardens themselves: to the children playing in them, the teachers using them, and the local communities benefiting from them. This included providing relief from thermal stress, creating more permeable spaces better at managing rainfall, educational benefits, active play spaces, increasing biodiversity and the human connection to this nature. Secondly, benefits more broadly to the city in terms of raising the profile of the value of a nature-based solution approach to urban design. Such has been the success of this project that proposals are underway to expand these approaches to other school settings and to deliver nature-based solution approaches to other spaces including more floating gardens and urban allotments.

Long-term impacts of the continued scaling of nature-based solution approaches in Poznań would include increased climate adaptation measures, greater opportunity for relaxation and experiencing nature, increased awareness of, and engagement with, active travel and the environment.

NBS benefits

- Increasing infiltration
- Reduce drought risk
- Reduce flood risk
- Reducing temperature at meso or micro scale
- Improve connectivity and functionality of green and blue infrastructures
- Increase biodiversity
- Increase quality and quantity of green and blue infrastructures
- Changing image of the urban environment
- Creation of green jobs relating to construction & maintenance of NBS
- Improve air quality
- Increase accessibility to green open spaces
- Increase amount of green open spaces for residents
- Increase awareness of NBS solution & their effectiveness and co benefits
- Increase communities' sense of ownership
- Increase social interaction
- Increase stakeholder awareness & knowledge about NBS
- Increase well-being
- Increase willingness to invest in NBS
- Provision of health benefits
- Social inclusion
- Social learning about location & importance of NBS

Transferability of the result:

A key outcome from the City of Poznań's involvement in the Connecting Nature project was the implementation of evaluation to understand the benefits and co-benefits of the approaches implemented. Previously in the city, evaluation of nature-based solution pilots was less structured. By formalising the evaluation and expanding it to include evaluation of environment, social, and economic benefits, it was possible to build a stronger and more communicable evidence-base for the benefits of the approach taken.

Within the City of Poznań, the results from the open and social gardens are already being transferred to other contexts. For example, expanding from the focus on kindergartens, to include primary and, potentially, secondary schools. Initiatives like the NBS catalogue are also being used to transfer nature-based solution approaches to other sectors, including housing developers. Expanding the approach to financing the nature-based solution gardens to include the private sector, also represents a transfer of approaches to different sectors, and an increase in the capacity being brought to mainstreaming nature-based solutions in the city.

In terms of transfer beyond the city, Poznań's approach to focusing on the transformation of educational establishment grounds, the collaborative approach between city departments and external stakeholders are all easily transferrable. This includes to other types of nature/play/learn spaces, and for other types of nature-based solutions.

Lessons learned:

Based on the Reflexive Monitoring Learning Experience Workshop outcomes (WP2 Task 2.2)

Technical Solutions:

- Learning associated with nature-based solution implementation is incremental. Lessons learned from the multifunctional development of areas at risk of flood along the River Warta, including the creation of city beaches and recreational facilities at the previously neglected riverside sites, provided inspiration for increasing the social and ecological potential of areas of the city centre, including strengthening the 'green wedge' (by consolidation and de-fragmentation of urban green).
- Opening collaborations with different departments has the potential to impact the type of technical solutions that are implemented, bringing in greater multifunctionality.
- Sometimes what appears to be a setback can become a step forward: Only securing budget for two playgrounds instead of five ended up being a benefit. It provided an opportunity to deepen and enrich the co-creation process to find more innovative solutions. It also led to a focus on developing other types of playgrounds for older children.
- Nature-based solution technical design out-scaling is not a copy and paste approach. Each time the concept is replicated there needs to be consideration of the local context. For example, older children have different learning and playspace needs that need to be reflected through technical designs.

- Challenges like COVID19 can be used as an opportunity to build capacity when implementation is not possible. For example, multimedia resources showcasing the eco-demonstrator approach during lockdown represented a technical solution themselves in relation to unlocking broader rollout and ensuring the quality of the approach beyond the Connecting Nature team and project.
- Interdepartmental collaboration towards a particular technical design for nature-based solutions can open up opportunities for collaboration in other contexts and locations.

Governance:

- Interdepartmental collaboration has been key to mainstreaming nature-based solutions and increasing the human and economic capacity for delivery.
- Expanding funding to new sources and departments leads to new relations. By opening up new collaborations with other departments to city districts and inhabitants to also include enterprises, it is possible to change a city team's practice, potentially broadening the discourse on how other partners use nature-based solutions.
- Looking at a city through a nature-based solution lens can lead to identifying new typologies and a history of nature-based solution use in urban planning. This can lead to opportunities to change the discourse around nature-based solutions and open the opportunity or new collaboration.
- Scaling-up interventions like the nature-oriented playgrounds requires a novel process to ensure the quality of the intervention and new skills for the team are also scaled.
- Identifying 'green' agents across city departments can be an effective method to generate influence beyond the immediate team.
- Organisational innovation can be necessary if silos are to be burst. Breaking open silos can raise awareness in relation to new initiatives that can adopt a nature-based solution approach.
- New legal regulations can be required to facilitate collaboration with commercial enterprises under new governance models. Working with commercial partners can be time-intensive at first but can lead to more-efficient practices and new financing opportunities in the long-run.
- Even a failed funding bid can lead to new collaborative ways of working, if it is based on a new working model between departments/stakeholder groups.
- Looking at your city through a nature-based solution lens can provide opportunities to talk and work with different departments and change the governance of nature-based solutions.
- EU projects can provide opportunities to develop new organisational structures and collaborations between departments.
- Lobbying politicians can be a useful governance practice for city nature-based solution teams to gain high-level support for budget decisions.
- Once successful pilots have been implemented, it is possible to change governance structures towards promoting nature-based solutions among other partners that can co-finance the solution.

Financing and business models:

- Complex technical designs can represent a barrier in relation to tenders/applications as it can be difficult to fit design proposals into the tender/application system.
- It is possible to engage commercial enterprises to co-finance public initiatives through linking civic budgets with corporate responsibility/sponsorship processes.
- Linking investment with educational value can be a mechanism for securing funding financing for nature-based solutions.
- Opportunities for sharing funding across departments and with district councils should be explored.

Nature-based enterprises:

- Part of scaling nature-based solutions includes scaling the nature-based economy associated with implementation. Sourcing financing to fund the projects may not be enough if there is not sufficient private sector capacity to design and develop the spaces. It may also be necessary to stimulate the development of nature-based enterprises to be able to deliver the new market demand.
- By changing the discourse and stimulating others to think about their work in relation to nature-based solutions, it is possible to create new opportunities for nature-based enterprises.

Co-production:

- Actor-mapping is a key preliminary step in co-production.
- Mainstreaming nature-based solutions needs collaboration with other city hall departments in order to maximise the multifunctionality and unlock the necessary expertise and capacity.
- Co-production can introduce changes to systems that will lead to the ongoing review, development, and delivery of new forms of support. Co-production therefore benefits from a culture of continuous learning about what has worked and what has not worked.
- When forming collaborations with private sector investment, there needs to be a clear offer for sponsors/businesses to be involved, but also the flexibility to co-create the offer with the schools and potential sponsor.
- Co-production is not a one-size-fits-all process. Involving primary school kids in the design, delivery and stewardship of nature-based solutions requires a different co-production process with novel tools (e.g. digital).
- Communicating about projects can be used as a catalyst for internal co-production.
- Co-production tools developed to increase knowledge/capacity for nature-based solution implementation can also be used as educational resources for schools.

Impact assessment:

- Indicators are vital for communicating the effectiveness of nature-based solution process to colleagues and external stakeholders.

- Exploring evaluation already undertaken across city departments, and supplementing this through partnerships with academia, is an effective way to implement impact monitoring.

Reflexive monitoring:

- The process of reflexive monitoring helped to break through barriers that the organisation encountered by providing a strategic overview of the situation, analysing gaps, and identifying resources and activities to fill them.
- Reflexive monitoring was a useful tool for managing scaling-out of nature-based solution project implementation across the city.
- Reflexivity helps users to see the broader picture of nature-based solution activities within the organization structure – the reflexive monitoring scheme gives a broader picture, both for the topic of nature-based solutions, and the scope of the organization.
- Reflexive monitoring helps to track all the different activities in teamwork. It allows time to reflect on the different collaborations and to make sure the short-term actions are aligned with the long-term goals of projects.

Financing:

- *Eco-demonstrators* – in 2018-2019, the project of eco-demonstrators was financed from Connecting Nature project budget (20 preschools). In the second half of 2019 and in 2020, these were funded through The Regional Environmental Fund in Poznań (21 preschools). This was not a sustainable source long-term though, so the financing approach needed to be diversified. A City budget was used in 2021 to fund eco-demonstrators project in 5 preschools.
- *Nature-orientated playgrounds* – the modernization of pre-school gardens was carried out by the Department of Education Poznań City Hall and the Poznań Civil Budget. This included a partnership financing approach combining the Dept of Education and City Civic budgets. The five-year programme from the Department of Education has now ended, so alternative budgets need to be identified. This year, one natural playground was funded directly by the council. This was due to the very limited budgets caused by the COVID19 pandemic. A new approach is currently being developed which uses alternative financing from the private sector to ‘sponsor’ the creation of the nature-orientated playgrounds.
- *The floating gardens* – in 2018-2019 the project of floating gardens was financed using the Connecting Nature project budget. From 2020, floating gardens were funded using the city budget – out-scaling floating gardens across the city.

Bringing cities to life, bringing life into cities

Deliverable 11 – Annex 4

Connecting Nature Framework - City narrative and figure instructions

DOCUMENT PROPERTIES

Nature Document	Deliverable 11 – Annex 4: Connecting Nature Framework - City narrative and figure instructions
Work Package	WP3
Task Leader	UEL
Authors	Lead authors: Pauline Georgiou Contributors: ?
Reviewers	
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Version	Date	Modifications made
1		

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CN Framework - City narrative and figure

Step-by-step instructions

City:

1) Identify and reflect on the impact of your **transformation points** (up to 10 transformation points per city). You can briefly describe why each transformation point was that important. Please add an estimated date when the transformation point took place (if applicable) and specify if the transformation point is linked to the planning, delivery and/or stewardship phase of your exemplar.

TRANSFORMATION POINTS	Reflect on the impact of this transformation point on your exemplar
1. Add title of transformation point	<i>Add description:</i> <i>Linked to phase:</i>
2. Add title of transformation point	<i>Add description:</i> <i>Linked to phase:</i>
3. Add title of transformation point	<i>Add description:</i> <i>Linked to phase:</i>
...	...

2) Identify and describe your **trademarks.** Out of the seven elements of the CN Framework, identify the most relevant elements for you during the three phases of the Framework and describe in which manner you considered and used it. To keep it simple, you should select only one or two elements.

TRADEMARKS	Phase		
	Planning	Delivery	Stewardship
<i>Add element (e.g., Impact Assessment)</i>	<i>Add description</i>	<i>Add description</i>	<i>Add description</i>
<i>Add element (e.g., Governance)</i>	<i>Add description</i>	<i>Add description</i>	<i>Add description</i>

3) Complete the following score table with the **degree of importance** for the seven **elements** of the CN Framework during the three phases (i.e., planning, delivery, stewardship).

Use values: High, Medium, Low.

ELEMENT	SCORE		
	Planning	Delivery	Stewardship
Technical solutions	<i>E.g., Low</i>	<i>E.g., Medium</i>	<i>E.g., High</i>
Governance	<i>Add value</i>	<i>Add value</i>	<i>Add value</i>
Financing & business models	<i>Add value</i>	<i>Add value</i>	<i>Add value</i>
Entrepreneurship	<i>Add value</i>	<i>Add value</i>	<i>Add value</i>
Co-production	<i>Add value</i>	<i>Add value</i>	<i>Add value</i>
Reflexive monitoring	<i>Add value</i>	<i>Add value</i>	<i>Add value</i>
Impact assessment	<i>Add value</i>	<i>Add value</i>	<i>Add value</i>

4) Complete the score table with **degree of development** of each **phase** of the CN Framework (i.e., planning, delivery and stewardship).

Use values: High, Medium, Low.

PHASE	Score
Planning	<i>E.g., Low</i>
Delivery	<i>Add value</i>
Stewardship	<i>Add value</i>

5) Include pictures that represent the evolution of your exemplar, from planning to delivery and stewardship (if applicable).